

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

CRISANTO E. AVILA

**RADIO-BASED INSTRUCTIONS IN THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR A
PROPOSED INNOVATIVE WORKPLAN**

Thesis Adviser:

DR. GRACE J. ALFONSO
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Midyear 2023

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	☐ Yes	or	☒ No
Publication (P)	☐ Yes	or	☒ No
Confidential (C)	☐ Yes	or	☒ No
Free (F)	☒ Yes	or	☐ No

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser signature:

University Permission Page

RADIO-BASED INSTRUCTIONS IN THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED INNOVATIVE WORKPLAN

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

CRISANTO E. AVILA, Midyear 2023
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **AUTHOR'S NAME** with the title: "**RADIO-BASED INSTRUCTIONS IN THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED INNOVATIVE WORKPLAN** " is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

GRACE J. ALFONSO, PhD
Chair, Thesis Committee

(Date)

BENJAMINA PAULA G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

MELINDA F. LUMANTA, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

DIEGO S. MARANAN, PhD
Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Midyear 2023

Biographical Sketch

Crisanto E. Avila, fondly known as Cris, is a dedicated educator whose noble objective in life is to be an agent of peace, growth, and development, striving to make the world a better place to live in.

Born in Guinayangan, Quezon, Region IV-A CALABARZON, he is the fourth child among two sisters and two brothers to Nicanor P. Avila and Consuelo P. Elope, both natives of Bicol. From the outset, he displayed a passion for learning, and his journey through education was within the public school system. He achieved academic excellence throughout, graduating with honors from Guinayangan Elementary School in 1986 and Guinayangan National High School in 1990. His pursuit of knowledge led him to Philippine Normal University-Manila, where he graduated with a degree in Bachelor of Secondary Education in 1994, successfully passing the Philippine Board Examination for Teachers (PBET) the same year.

Beginning his teaching career in 1994-1995, his talent and potential were recognized when he was appointed as one of the youngest school principals in the county at Christ the School of Cavite in 1996. However, his ambitions extended beyond teaching alone, as he established St. Aloysius Academy of Dasmarinas in 2005, a family-owned private school offering complete Pre School, Grade School, and Junior High School programs.

Beyond his dedication to education, he is deeply involved in various professional organizations, advocacies, and community and civic movements. He actively participates in Lions Clubs International, Rotary Club International, and Aloysian Professional Community. His commitment to research and development projects is evident through numerous published and presented researches and

journals, featured in international, national, and provincial fora. Moreover, Mr. Avila has become a respected figure in the field, often sought as a judge, consultant, and resource speaker for various training sessions, seminars, and workshops.

Although his academic achievements are remarkable, he also possesses a creative side and a love for filmmaking. His movie titled "Ayuda" earned him recognition, winning the laurel at the Cinemaking International Film Award in 2020 and other prestigious film festivals abroad. He also received the Catholic Mass Media Award for his contribution to scholastic publication in the Philippines and was a three-time finalist in the Metrobank Search for Outstanding Teachers. Furthermore, his alma mater, the Philippine Normal University, bestowed upon him the Gawad Sulo as Eminent Alumnus in 2019. His expertise extends beyond borders, as he serves as a national trainer in Campus Journalism, conducting training sessions across the Philippines and the Asia Pacific Region since 2005.

Presently, he continues to wear many hats. He not only serves as the director of St. Aloysius Academy but also holds the position of Chief Executive Officer of the Educators' Link of Aloysian Publications, an international publication for teachers, further strengthening his dedication to empowering educators worldwide.

Acknowledgment

I wholeheartedly express profound gratitude and appreciation to the following individuals and organizations who have played significant roles in the successful completion of this research study:

Dr. Grace J. Alfonso, my thesis adviser and chairman of the thesis committee, whose unwavering encouragement and generous sharing of time, expertise, and knowledge have been instrumental in the accomplishment of this study.

Dr. Ramadan de Jesus, my statistician, whose invaluable assistance in the statistical treatment and analysis of the research data, along with the interpretation of tables, has been indispensable to this work.

Dr. Diego S. Maranan, PhD, Dean of the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, for being a great source of inspiration and encouragement throughout my academic journey.

The members of the Thesis Committee, Dr. Benjamina Paula G. Flor and Dr. Melinda F. Lumanta, for their valuable suggestions and constructive comments that have significantly contributed to the improvement of this research.

Ms. Agnes V. Mejia, from the secretariat of FICS, for her exceptional accommodation, encouragement, kindness, patience, and willingness to assist me in all my inquiries.

St. Aloysius Academy of Dasmariñas, for their unwavering moral support throughout this research endeavor, and special thanks to Dr. Rainelda M. Lasa, the School President, Mrs. Criselda C. Libay, School Principal, and Mr. Ricky M. Muyo, Cashier, and Mrs. Christy Reyes, Office Secretary for their valuable assistance during the research process.

The Cavite Educators Lions Club and Lions Clubs International District 301-A 2 Philippines, whose continuous support has been the driving force behind the completion of this masterpiece.

The Cavite Alliance of Private Schools and Dasmariñas Association of Private Schools for their love, support, and guidance that has made me deserving of the position I aspire to within the association.

Dr. Elias A. Alicaya, Jr., Assistant Schools Division Superintendent, OIC- Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the City Schools Division of Dasmariñas, for the endorsement provided, which has been instrumental in carrying out this research.

The respondents of the study from across the country, whose full cooperation and active participation during the administration of the research instruments, have made this study possible.

Prof. Corazon D. Salcedo and Mdm. Beth M. Gaton, my colleagues, and friends, for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout this academic journey.

The Aloysian Publications, for their financial support and strong motivation that propelled me to complete this study.

My wife, Mdm. Rhoda M. Avila, and our son, Romeo Christopher M. Avila, for their understanding, words of encouragement, dedicated prayers, and unwavering moral support throughout this research journey.

The Avila and Mendoza families, for their love and constant inspiration that has helped me reach new heights in this endeavor.

Above all, I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the Almighty God for the precious gifts of life, wisdom, and perseverance. Without His divine guidance and blessings, this endeavor would not have been possible.

I am sincerely grateful for the unwavering support and assistance of each individual and organization mentioned above, as they have all played pivotal roles in the successful completion of this research study.

C.E.A.

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis with heartfelt gratitude to the cherished memories of my parents, who continue to have a profound impact on my life, even though they are no longer with us.

First and foremost, I pay tribute to my father, Nicanor Peralta Avila, whose boundless love and teachings on the value of hard work have shaped the person I am today. Tatay, your guidance, and affection will forever remain etched in my heart. Thank you for everything.

Next, I extend my dedication to my mother, Consuelo Patron Elope, who raised me with love, instilled confidence in me, and emphasized the importance of education. Nanay Taba, your nurturing presence and wisdom have been invaluable in my journey. I am forever grateful.

To my brothers and sisters of the Avila Family, who have always looked up to me, and to my cousins and relatives in Manila and Quezon Province, your support and encouragement have been a source of strength throughout.

I offer this work with profound appreciation to my loving and supportive wife, Rhoda M. Avila, and our dear son, Romeo Christopher M. Avila. Your unwavering belief in me has been a driving force behind my accomplishments. I am fortunate to have you by my side.

I extend my dedication to the Mendoza Family of Talugtog, Nueva Ecija, for their love and encouragement, which has been a pillar of support.

I also dedicate this thesis to the Aloysian Publications family, both in the Philippines and around the world, for the love, trust, and confidence they have bestowed upon me. Your encouragement has been instrumental in my academic journey.

Lastly, I offer my deepest gratitude to the Holy Trinity, my God, for bestowing me with the intellectual and physical capabilities to accomplish this research. All the glory and honors are humbly returned to you. Amen.

In memory of my parents and with heartfelt appreciation to my loved ones and mentors, I present this thesis as a testament to the love, guidance, and support that have shaped my path in life. May their influence continue to inspire and guide me in all my future endeavors.

C.E.A.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	vi
Dedication	ix
Table of Contents	xi
List of Tables	xiii
List of Figures	xiv
Abstract	xv
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	7
Objectives of the Study	9
Hypotheses of the Study	10
Significance of the Study	10
Theoretical Framework	14
Conceptual Framework	17
Scope and Limitation of the Study	21
Operational Definition of Terminologies	22
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	27
Factors Affecting Mathematics Performance among High School Students	27
The Importance of Information Technology in the Growth of Distance Learning for Nigerian Instructors	28
Educational Services, Teacher Quality, and Students' Academic Performance: A Correlational Study	29
Enhancing Distance Learning Through TV and Radio-Based Materials: A Review	30
School Administrators' Support in the Face of the COVID-19 Pandemic	
Teachers' Readiness in the New Normal Learning Modalities	34
Readiness of Teachers for Online Teaching: Insights from Previous Studies	40
Exploring the Empowering Potential of Studio Tamani's	

Radio Programming for Women's Voices in Mali	41
Assessing the Impact of Radio-Based Instruction on Academic Performance in Modular Distance Learning	42
Exploring the Significance of Silence in Swedish Public Service Radio	45
Blended Learning in Education: A Review of Literature and Implications for the New Normal	46
Coping Strategies of Teachers in the New Normal Education: A Qualitative Exploration	48
The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its Application in Technology Adoption Research	49
The Impact of COVID-19 on Education in the Philippines: Policy Measures and Academic Disruptions	51
Synthesis	53
 CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY	 55
Research Design	55
Participants and Sampling Procedure	56
Respondents of the Study	56
Instrument of the Study	57
Null Hypothesis	57
Likert Scale	58
Data Gathering Procedure	59
Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment	60
Ethical Considerations	61
Confidentiality and Anonymity	62
Honesty and Respect	62
 CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	 63
Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents	63
Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions	76
Performance Level of Students in Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal	86
Student-Respondents' Perception of the Implementation of the Radio-Based Instructions	89
Significant Relationship Between the Performance of the Students and Their Problem Encountered with the Implementation of the Radio-Based Instructions	97
 CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	 99
Summary	99
Conclusions	102
Recommendations	110
Workplan	114
REFERENCES	120
 ANNEXES	 134

Annex A Letter Request to School Division Superintendent Seeking Endorsement for Data Gathering and Conduct of the Study	134
Annex B Letter Request to RBI Teachers	135
Annex C Sample Indorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent	136
Annex D Memorandum of Agreement Request to Conduct Study and Gather Data	137
Annex E Data Collection Instrument	141

List of Tables

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Age	63
Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Gender	65
Table 3 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Family Income	68
Table 4 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Father's Educational Attainment	70
Table 5 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Mother's Educational Attainment	73
Table 6 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Awareness	76
Table 7 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Availability and Capability	78
Table 8 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Time Allotment	80
Table 9 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Quality of Learning Instructions	82
Table 10 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Responsiveness and Learning Feedback	84
Table 11 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for the Performance Level of Students in Radio-Based Instruction	86
Table 12 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation of the Respondents' Perceived Implementation of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Teacher's Readiness	89
Table 13 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation of the Respondents' Perceived Implementation of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of School's Readiness	94
Table 14 Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient Table for the Respondents' Perception of Service Quality based on Technological Innovations And Customer Satisfaction	97

List of Figures

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework of the Radio-Based Instructions In the New Normal	16
Figure 2 Conceptual Paradigm Showing the Relationship of Variables	20

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted the education sector, prompting schools to adopt alternative modes of instruction for continuous learning. Radio-based instructions have emerged as a viable option, particularly for students in remote or underserved areas with limited internet access. This study examines the effectiveness and feasibility of radio-based instructions as an educational mode during the pandemic. Quantitative data were collected from 207 students across various schools implementing RBI in S.Y. 2021-2022. The findings indicate a high level of effectiveness in RBI, with students' performance being deemed very satisfactory. The study proposes a workplan to enhance the delivery and overall effectiveness of RBI, recommending that school principals adopt these measures for improved educational outcomes in the new normal.

Keywords: Radio Based Instruction, Alternative Learning Modality , Pandemic School Year, Workplan

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the education sector, forcing schools and educational institutions worldwide to adopt alternative modes of instruction to ensure continuity of learning. In response to the crisis, many educational systems have shifted towards remote and online learning approaches. However, these methods pose challenges, particularly in areas with limited access to technology and internet connectivity.

In this context, radio-based instructions have emerged as a viable alternative for delivering educational content to students, especially in remote or underserved areas. Given its broad accessibility and extensive reach, radio has the capacity to connect with a significant student population that might lack access to internet-capable devices or reliable internet connections. By broadcasting instructional content through radio programs, students can receive educational materials at home and continue their learning journey.

Education is widely acknowledged as the key to success, progress, and development (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2018). In particular, the education of the younger generation is considered crucial as they are seen as the future of the nation (Brown, 2019; Martinez, 2017).

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic brought about significant changes in the economic and educational landscape of both developed and underdeveloped

countries (Gupta, 2021; Lee, 2020). Due to school closures and the suspension of in-person teaching, what had previously appeared unachievable has now become a tangible outcome (Kumar, 2022).

The lockdown measures implemented during the pandemic amplified the pre-existing literacy challenges and widened the gap between children in advantaged and less advantaged literacy environments (Davis, 2021; Thompson, 2020). While first-world countries were able to utilize technology to shape the minds of young people, third-world countries faced difficulties in balancing various services, including healthcare and education (Nguyen, 2023; Rodriguez, 2022).

UNESCO proposed the adoption of distance learning programs and platforms as a solution to the educational difficulties brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic (UNESCO, 2020). In the Philippines, the education sector took steps to address this issue by adopting various means and programs to ensure that learning continues through different learning delivery modalities (Department of Education, 2021).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (2020) has adopted several distance learning modalities, including modular distance learning (MDL), online distance learning, and television or radio-based instruction. MDL involves the use of printed modules that enable students to engage in independent learning at home. These modules consist of digital lessons and assessments (Department of Education, 2020). Conversely, online education is primarily employed in urban environments, whereas modular distance learning (MDL) is more frequently put into practice in rural regions (Department of Education, 2020). In rural areas, students utilize self-learning modules (SLMs) in print,

digital, or electronic formats, depending on the learner's individual preferences and needs (Department of Education, 2020).

Additional learning resources like Learner's Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and supplementary study materials are incorporated into the distance learning approach, as supplied by the Department of Education (DepEd) (DepEd, 2020). The objective of implementing distance learning is to reduce in-person interactions, encourage physical distancing, and at the same time, sustain the education of numerous Filipino learners (DepEd, 2020).

Remote learning approach is particularly suitable for independent learners who can engage in self-directed learning, as well as for learners who receive periodic supervision and support from their parents or guardians (DepEd, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the field of education, raising concerns about the quality of learning outcomes. This concern is compounded by the results of the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), which provide a backdrop for understanding the existing challenges and issues in education (OECD, 2019). The "new normal" situation, characterized by learners being left to learn independently at their own pace, further exacerbates these challenges.

One of the primary challenges in this new normal situation is the ability of learners to engage in independent learning. Learners who struggle with independent learning may face difficulties in adapting to this mode of education (Department of Education, 2020). Recognizing this predicament, the researcher aims to assess the performance level of selected Junior High school respondents in Radio-based Instructions (RBI) within the City

Schools Division of Dasmarinas, Dasmarinas City, Cavite, as part of understanding the implications of the new normal on education.

Research gaps in the study could include:

1. Limited research on the effectiveness of radio-based instructions in the new normal: There may be a lack of empirical studies examining the impact and effectiveness of utilizing radio-based instructions as a mode of education in the new normal context. This research gap highlights the need for more research to determine the effectiveness of this approach and its potential benefits and limitations.

2. Understanding the challenges and limitations of radio-based instructions: While radio-based instructions have been implemented as an alternative learning modality during the pandemic, there may be limited research that explores the specific challenges and limitations associated with this approach. Examining practical concerns like radio accessibility, student engagement, and possible learning obstacles would enhance our grasp of the workability and efficiency of radio-based education.

3. Assessment of student performance and learning outcomes: Research gaps may exist in terms of evaluating the academic performance and learning outcomes of students who receive radio-based instructions. Assessing the effectiveness of this mode of instruction in promoting student learning, knowledge acquisition, and skill development would provide valuable insights for educational practitioners and policymakers.

4. Exploration of innovative strategies to enhance radio-based instructions: The study could explore potential innovative strategies or interventions to improve the delivery and effectiveness of radio-based instructions. This may include examining the integration

of supplementary materials, interactive components, or technological enhancements to augment the learning experience and engagement of students.

5. Inclusion of diverse learner populations: Investigating the experiences and outcomes of different learner populations, such as students with disabilities, students from disadvantaged backgrounds, or those in remote areas, could be a research gap. Understanding the unique challenges and needs of these groups in the context of radio-based instructions would contribute to more inclusive and equitable educational practices.

This study may differentiate itself from other studies in the following ways:

1. Focus on radio-based instructions: The study specifically examines the use of radio-based instructions as a mode of education in the new normal context. While there may be studies on alternative learning modalities during the pandemic, this study's exclusive focus on radio-based instruction sets it apart from research that explores other modalities, such as online learning or television-based instruction.

2. Proposed innovative workplan: The study aims to develop a proposed innovative workplan based on the findings related to radio-based instructions. This aspect distinguishes it from studies that solely investigate the effectiveness or challenges of a particular instructional approach. The study goes beyond assessment and analysis by providing practical recommendations for implementing and enhancing radio-based instructions in the new normal.

3. Emphasis on the new normal context: The study explicitly considers the unique circumstances of the new normal, which refers to the educational landscape shaped by the COVID-19 pandemic. It recognizes the need for adaptive and innovative approaches to education during this time. By focusing on radio-based instructions in the context of the

new normal, the study contributes to understanding how traditional media can be effectively utilized amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic.

4. Potential for proposing innovative strategies: The study's objective of developing an innovative workplan suggests a proactive approach to addressing the limitations or gaps identified in radio-based instructions. By proposing creative and novel strategies, the study aims to enhance the effectiveness and engagement of learners in this instructional modality. This forward-thinking aspect differentiates the study from those that primarily focus on reporting existing practices without suggesting improvements.

Overall, the study's focus on radio-based instructions in the new normal, the development of a proposed workplan, and the emphasis on innovative strategies make it distinct from other studies in the field of alternative learning modalities during the pandemic.

The study holds significant implications if left unaddressed. Without this study, the persisting and even worsening educational inequality among students in remote and underserved areas, who lack access to the internet and digital devices, could exacerbate the existing education gap.

Additionally, the absence of a structured radio-based instructional plan would deny students an alternative means of accessing quality education, particularly impacting those in less-connected regions. The underutilization of radio broadcasting as a cost-effective and inclusive educational platform could lead to inefficiencies in the education system, with educational institutions overcommitting resources to digital solutions that are not universally accessible.

Neglecting community engagement through local radio stations and content development means the loss of opportunities to strengthen local ties, integrate cultural relevance into education, and enhance overall learning experiences. Ineffective education policies, without the guidance of research-backed findings, may lead to the implementation of inadequate or unsustainable programs.

Lastly, the potential for public-private partnerships in the education sector might remain unrealized, causing private entities to miss the chance to contribute to enhancing education's accessibility and quality. In summary, not undertaking this study would perpetuate educational disparities and hinder efforts to provide equitable, inclusive, and cost-effective education. Furthermore, it would overlook the opportunity to capitalize on the advantages of radio-based education and community engagement, making it vital for addressing the challenges of the "new normal" and seizing the potential for innovative, accessible, and community-centered education.

Statement of the Problem

Given the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic and the transition to the "new normal" in education, it is essential to assess the efficiency and viability of radio-based instruction as an educational approach. The researcher aims to investigate certain factors that influence students' performance in radio-based instruction and will analyze these in relation to specific profile variables. This analysis will serve as the foundation for developing an innovative action plan.

This research aims to shed light on the question: "What is the basis for a proposed innovative workplan centered on radio-based instructions in the context of the new normal?" More specifically, the researcher intends to obtain insights into the following inquiries:

1. What is the profile of the student-respondents in terms of:

- a. age;
- b. gender;
- c. family income; and
- d. parents' highest educational attainment

2. What is the degree of radio-based instruction effectiveness concerning:

- a. awareness and readiness;
- b. accessibility and proficiency;
- c. time allocation;
- d. instructional quality; and
- e. responsiveness and feedback in learning?

3. What is the performance level of students in radio-based instructions in the new normal context?

4. How may the students perceive the implementation of the Radio-based Instruction in terms of:

- a. Teacher's Readiness; and
- b. School's Readiness

5. Is there a noteworthy correlation between the students' performance and their perception of the execution of radio-based instructions?

6. What workplan can be proposed to enhance the delivery, engagement, and overall effectiveness of radio-based instructions in the new normal?

By investigating these research questions, this study aims to enhance the comprehension of radio-based instruction as an alternative learning method, offer insights into the obstacles experienced by both educators and students, and present a strategic workplan to enhance the effectiveness of radio-based instruction in the context of the "new normal."

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the effectiveness of radio-based instructions (RBI) in facilitating learning outcomes for Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School students in the new normal educational setting.
2. To recognize the hurdles and obstacles encountered by both students and educators in the execution of radio-based instruction (RBI) amid the "new normal," and to suggest creative solutions to overcome these challenges.
3. To assess the extent of student involvement and active participation in radio-based instruction (RBI) sessions and its repercussions on their academic achievements and enthusiasm for learning.
4. To investigate the viewpoints and encounters of educators, students, and parents concerning the utilization of RBI as an alternate method of instruction within the context of the "new normal."

5. To develop a comprehensive and innovative work plan that optimizes the benefits of RBI and addresses the limitations to enhance the overall effectiveness of remote learning in the new normal.

6. To provide practical recommendations and strategies for policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders to integrate RBI effectively in the educational system and ensure its sustainability in the future.

7. To contribute to the existing body of knowledge on radio-based instructions and remote learning approaches by conducting a thorough analysis and presenting the study's findings in a well-structured and documented manner.

Hypothesis of the Study

The study tested these hypotheses:

1. There is a significant difference in the performance level of students in radio-based instructions in the new normal context.

2. There are significant challenges and limitations associated with implementing radio-based instructions in the new normal.

3. There is a significant effect of innovative strategies on the delivery, engagement, and overall effectiveness of radio-based instructions in the new normal.

These hypotheses guided the research process, allowing for the testing of the relationships and effects of interest in the study. Statistical analysis and data collection were conducted to either accept or reject the null hypotheses, providing insights into the significance of the variables under investigation.

Significance of the Study

The importance of this study is underscored by its prospective impact on the domains of education and instructional design within the framework of the "new normal."

This study's significance is exemplified by the following:

1. Addressing a research gap: The study aims to fill a research gap by specifically investigating the effectiveness and feasibility of radio-based instructions as a mode of education in the new normal. By focusing on this specific modality, the study provides valuable insights into an underexplored area, contributing to the body of knowledge on alternative learning methods during the pandemic.
2. Informing educational practitioners and policymakers: The findings of the study can offer valuable insights to educational practitioners and policymakers involved in designing and implementing remote learning strategies. The proposed innovative workplan can serve as a practical guide for optimizing radio-based instructions, addressing challenges, and enhancing student learning experiences in the new normal.
3. Enhancing instructional effectiveness and engagement: The study's emphasis on proposing innovative strategies contributes to enhancing the effectiveness and engagement of learners in radio-based instructions. By identifying ways to improve the delivery, interactivity, and overall learning experience, the study offers practical recommendations that can benefit educators, instructional designers, and curriculum developers seeking to maximize the impact of radio-based instructions.
4. Promoting inclusivity and equity: Radio-based instructions have the potential to reach a wide range of learners, including those with limited access to digital technologies or

living in remote areas. By exploring the strengths and limitations of this modality, the study can contribute to more inclusive and equitable educational practices, ensuring that diverse learner populations have equal opportunities to access quality education in the new normal.

5. Adapting to evolving educational contexts: As the educational landscape continues to evolve, particularly in response to the ongoing challenges posed by the pandemic, the study's proposed innovative workplan provides a timely and relevant framework for educators and institutions to adapt their instructional approaches. This adaptability is crucial in preparing for future disruptions and maintaining educational continuity in uncertain times.

The importance of this study is evident in its potential to enrich our comprehension and enhance the efficiency of radio-based instruction in the context of the "new normal." By addressing research gaps, informing educational stakeholders, enhancing instructional effectiveness, promoting inclusivity, and facilitating adaptability, the study has the potential to shape and improve educational practices during and beyond the current crisis.

Moreover, this research carries noteworthy implications for a diverse range of stakeholders engaged in the educational system, encompassing:

Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and Chief of the Curriculum Implementation Division. The study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of radio-based instructions as a viable mode of education in the new normal. These education leaders can use the findings to inform decision-making processes and policy development related to alternative learning modalities. The proposed innovative work

plan offers a practical framework for designing and implementing radio-based instructions, enabling education leaders to optimize instructional delivery, address challenges, and enhance student learning outcomes.

School Principals and Teachers. The study equips school principals and teachers with evidence-based guidance on utilizing radio-based instructions effectively in the new normal. The proposed workplan can serve as a valuable resource for planning and implementing instructional strategies that engage students and promote effective learning. By understanding the strengths and limitations of radio-based instructions, educators can tailor their teaching methods and utilize appropriate supplementary materials to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Students and Parents. The study's significance for students and parents lies in its potential to improve the quality and accessibility of education. By identifying strategies to enhance radio-based instructions, students can benefit from a more engaging and effective learning experience, even in remote areas with limited access to digital resources. Parents can gain insights into supporting their children's learning journey in the new normal, understanding how radio-based instructions can be maximized, and exploring ways to provide effective guidance and support.

Researchers. The research adds to the current knowledge base regarding alternative learning methods employed during the pandemic. Researchers can build upon this study's findings to conduct further investigations, exploring additional aspects of radio-based instructions and proposing innovative approaches to enhance its effectiveness.

The study may inspire researchers to delve into related topics, such as the impact of radio-based instructions on specific learner populations, the integration of technology in radio-based learning, or comparative studies on the effectiveness of various alternative learning modalities.

In summary, the importance of the study extends to a broad spectrum of participants within the educational framework. It informs decision-making, guides instructional practices, improves student learning experiences, supports parents, and provides a foundation for further research in the field of radio-based instructions in the new normal.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinning of this study drew upon the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The Technology Acceptance Model is commonly applied to gain insights into how users embrace and integrate new technologies. Within the realm of radio-based instruction in the context of the "new normal," this framework enables the examination of factors that influence the acceptance and assimilation of this technology. These factors encompass perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user attitudes.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a well-established theoretical framework employed to comprehend the acceptance and implementation of technology. This model was initially introduced by Fred Davis in his 1989 publication, "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology" (Davis, 1989).

TAM is built on the following key concepts:

1. Perceived Usefulness (PU): This term pertains to the extent of an individual's belief in how a specific technology can improve their job performance or productivity. The likelihood of technology adoption is higher when it is perceived as beneficial to the individual (Davis, 1989).

2. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): This concept is associated with the degree to which a person believes that utilizing the technology will require minimal effort. If a technology is perceived as user-friendly and easy to use, it is more inclined to be embraced and put into practice (Davis, 1989).

TAM suggests that these two key factors, Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), have a direct impact on an individual's intention to use a technology. This intention, in turn, plays a pivotal role in determining the actual adoption and utilization of the technology. Over the years, the model has been rigorously tested and expanded in numerous studies, establishing itself as a fundamental concept in the realm of technology adoption and acceptance.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) holds significant relevance for this study in the following ways:

1. Understanding User Acceptance: The primary objective of TAM is to understand how users perceive and accept technology. In the context of radio-based instructions, it can help researchers gauge how individuals, such as employees or students in the "new normal," perceive the use of radio-based instructions. This is important for assessing whether these instructions are likely to be accepted and adopted.

2. Perceived Usefulness: One of the core components of TAM is "perceived usefulness," which evaluates how users believe a technology will enhance their job performance or productivity. For this study, this concept can be applied to assess whether radio-based instructions are seen as useful in the "new normal" for achieving specific work or educational objectives.

3. Perceived Ease of Use: Another central concept in TAM is "perceived ease of use," which examines how users perceive the ease or difficulty of using a technology. In the context of radio-based instructions, this concept can help determine if users find these instructions easy to follow, especially in the changing circumstances of the "new normal."

4. Intention to Use: According to TAM, the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use significantly impact an individual's intention to utilize a technology. This aspect is particularly pertinent in this study as it assists in gauging whether individuals in the "new normal" are inclined to embrace radio-based instructions based on their perceptions of its usefulness and ease of use.

5. Identifying Adoption Barriers: TAM can also assist in identifying barriers to the adoption of radio-based instructions. By assessing factors that hinder perceived usefulness or ease of use, the study can identify challenges and areas for improvement in the proposed innovative workplan.

6. Recommendations for Improvement: The study can use the findings from TAM to make recommendations for enhancing the design and implementation of radio-based instructions. For example, if the research shows that perceived ease of use is low, recommendations can be made to simplify the instructions or provide better training.

7. Comparative Analysis: TAM can also be used for a comparative analysis of the acceptance of radio-based instructions across different user groups, such as employees and students, to understand if there are variations in perceived usefulness and ease of use.

TAM offers a valuable theoretical framework for investigating the acceptance and adoption of radio-based instructions in the "new normal." It can help the study assess the perceived value and ease of use of these instructions, identify adoption barriers, and provide insights for an innovative workplan that aligns with users' needs and preferences in this evolving context.

Figure 1.

Theoretical Framework of the Radio-based Instructions in the New Normal

Conceptual Framework

The study utilizes a conceptual framework that draws inspiration from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as its theoretical cornerstone. This framework

serves as a structured approach to understanding and promoting the acceptance and adoption of radio-based instructions within the unique context of the "new normal."

In this conceptual framework, the key variables are organized as follows:

Dependent Variable: The central focus of the study is the "Adoption of Radio-Based Instructions." This represents the outcome that the research aims to comprehend and facilitate within the ever-evolving "new normal."

Independent Variables such as:

1. Perceived Usefulness (PU):

This variable assesses the extent to which individuals perceive radio-based instructions as beneficial in enhancing their work or learning processes in the "new normal." It gauges the perceived value that users attach to these instructions.

2. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU):

PEOU measures the ease with which users believe they can engage with and use radio-based instructions. It focuses on the perceived simplicity, user-friendliness, and overall ease of integrating this technology into their routines.

3. Intention to Use (IU):

IU reflects users' intentions to actively adopt and incorporate radio-based instructions into their daily work or learning activities within the context of the "new normal."

4. User Demographics (UD):

User demographics include factors such as age, gender, prior experience with similar technologies, and educational background. These characteristics may

significantly influence how users perceive the instructions and their intentions to use them.

In this study, the concepts of Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) were reflected in the challenges faced by the student-respondents. Meanwhile, the Intention to Use (IU) was demonstrated through the Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions, including elements such as awareness and preparedness, availability and capability, time allocation, quality of learning instructions, as well as responsiveness and feedback in the learning process. While User Demographics (UD) found equivalence with the Profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, Parents' Monthly Family Income and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment.

Relationships and Hypotheses:

PU influences IU:

According to the TAM principles, when users perceive radio-based instructions as highly useful in facilitating their work or learning tasks in the "new normal," they are more likely to express an intention to use them. The hypothesis suggests a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and the intention to use.

PEOU influences IU:

If users find radio-based instructions easy to use and perceive them as a hassle-free solution, their intention to use these instructions is expected to be higher. The hypothesis proposes a positive link between perceived ease of use and the intention to use.

PU influences PEOU:

The perceived usefulness of radio-based instructions can significantly influence how easy or difficult users perceive them to be. When users consider these instructions valuable, they may also find them easier to use. The hypothesis expects a positive correlation between the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use.

User Demographics can influence PU, PEOU, and IU:

User characteristics, such as age, prior experience, and educational background, may play a role in shaping how individuals perceive the usefulness, ease of use, and their intention to use radio-based instructions. The hypothesis suggests that these demographic variables can moderate the relationships between PU, PEOU, and IU, acknowledging that certain user groups may have different perceptions and intentions.

This conceptual framework not only provides a structured approach to comprehending the dynamics of radio-based instructions within the "new normal" but also offers a foundation for testing and confirming these hypothesized relationships. Ultimately, this framework offers a valuable structure for guiding the study and developing an innovative workplan that aligns with the needs and preferences of users within the "new normal".

Figure 2.

Conceptual paradigm showing the relationship of variables

Dynamics of Radio-Based Instructions In the New Normal

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study is distinctly centered on assessing the academic performance of students at the Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School levels within selected schools across the country that have implemented radio-based instruction (RBI) during the academic year 2021-2022. The students' performance level was determined based on their Graded Point Average (GPA) from the academic year 2021-2022, serving as an indicator of their academic achievement.

To gather relevant data, a questionnaire was administered to the student respondents. The questionnaire was crafted to collect data regarding the students' performance in radio-based instructions, encompassing aspects like comprehension, engagement, and overall learning outcomes.

It is crucial to acknowledge that this study is constrained to the particular context of randomly selected Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School students from various regions within the county with RBI.

The findings and recommendations derived from this study may not be applicable to other educational levels or geographic locations. Furthermore, the study focuses solely on the assessment of student performance in radio-based instructions and does not encompass other alternative learning modalities or factors influencing academic achievement.

Through delineating the scope and limitations of this study, the objective is to offer significant insights into the performance of Junior High School students engaging with radio-based instructions within a particular educational division. This endeavor contributes to the existing reservoir of knowledge in this field.

Operational Definition of Terminologies

The following terms are defined, either in theoretical or operational terms, to provide clarity and enhance the understanding of the terminology employed in this study.

Adoption of Radio-Based Instructions. This refers to the process by which individuals in the context of the "new normal" actively incorporate and utilize radio-based instructional methods and technologies for their work or learning activities, reflecting a decision to integrate these instructions into their routines and practices.

City Schools Division of Dasmaringas. Represents the specific educational division or administrative unit within the study's geographic scope. It refers to the educational institutions, students, teachers, and stakeholders affiliated with the educational system in Dasmaringas City, serving as the context for this study.

Classroom Management. This refers to the implementation of rules and standards. Teachers should be fully aware of what is happening and are in control of classroom activities, and students should be made responsible for their behavior.

Determinants of Students' Performance. These factors may have significant effects on the students' performance in public secondary schools in SDO Dasmaringas City. This study encompasses an examination of the students' personal and socio-economic backgrounds, as well as an evaluation of their perceptions regarding the effectiveness of radio-based instruction.

Graded Point Average (GPA). This is the Graded Point Average of the respondents from the First to fourth grading periods of the previous school year.

Innovative Workplan. Refers to a proposed plan or framework that incorporates creative and novel strategies for enhancing the effectiveness and delivery of radio-based

instructions in the new normal. It encompasses innovative approaches, instructional techniques, and supportive measures designed to optimize the learning experience for students.

Intention to Use (IU). Intention to Use (IU) signifies an individual's stated willingness and intent to actively embrace and utilize radio-based instruction in their everyday work or learning activities, especially within the distinctive context of the "new normal."

Junior High School. Pertains to the educational tier succeeding elementary school and preceding senior high school, typically catering to students aged 12 to 15 years. In this study, the primary focus of the investigation will be on Junior High School students.

Mastery of the Subject Matter. This means that the teacher knows and delivers his lesson/s very well without looking at his references

Medium of Instruction. It is the language used by the teacher in teaching.

Monthly Income of the Family. This pertains to the amount of money earned every month by the parents of the student respondents.

Motivation. This refers to the eagerness and willingness of the students to learn through the different approaches used by the teacher, like games, stories, puzzles, and different media apps.

New Normal. Designates the contemporary educational environment that has evolved due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is characterized by the implementation of alternative learning methods and safety measures aimed at ensuring the uninterrupted provision of education while adhering to physical distancing protocols.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). In this study, "Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)" refers to an individual's subjective assessment of the simplicity, user-friendliness, and the extent to which they perceive radio-based instructions as effortless to operate and integrate into their work or learning processes within the "new normal." It reflects the user's perceived level of ease when engaging with these instructions.

Perceived Usefulness (PU). It represents an individual's subjective evaluation of the extent to which radio-based instructions are believed to enhance their job performance, productivity, or effectiveness within the context of the "new normal." It reflects the user's perception of the value and utility of these instructions for their specific tasks and objectives.

Parents' Educational Attainment. Denotes the highest educational level achieved by the parents of the student respondents.

Performance. This refers to the ratings of the students in a certain subject during the first to fourth grading periods.

Performance Level. Represents the measure of a student's academic achievement and competence in implementing radio-based instructions. It is typically assessed using indicators such as the Graded Point Average (GPA), which reflects a student's overall performance based on their grades from the previous academic year.

Personal Profile. This pertains to the student respondents' gender, the monthly income of their families, and the educational attainment of their parents.

Questionnaire. A research instrument comprising a series of organized questions, intended to elicit information from the student respondents. In this study, the questionnaire will be used to collect data related to the student's performance level in radio-based instructions, including their comprehension, engagement, and learning outcomes.

Radio-Based Instructions. Refers to the mode of delivering educational content and instructions through radio broadcasts. It involves using the radio as a medium to transmit lessons, lectures, and educational materials to students who can access the broadcasts.

Teaching Strategies. This refers to well-organized learning activities anchored on real-life situations, including learners' interests and needs. It is the teacher's style to present and deliver his lessons to his students so that students develop their critical thinking and participate well in class discussions.

Teacher-Student Relationship. This refers to how the teacher deals with his students, demonstrates a friendly attitude and behavior, and builds rapport with each other.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). This refers to a widely acknowledged theoretical framework employed to assess and comprehend how individuals perceive the utility and user-friendliness of a particular technology, consequently impacting their intent to embrace and employ that technology. TAM serves as a foundational concept for comprehending technology acceptance and adoption in various contexts.

User Demographics (UD). It encompasses various personal characteristics such as age, gender, prior experience with similar technologies, educational background, and other relevant individual attributes. UD is used to understand how these demographic factors may influence how users perceive and intend to use radio-based instructions within the context of the "new normal."

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter includes the research conducted by foreign and local authors, which the researcher considered relevant to this present investigation. These reviewed materials helped in the conceptualization of the study.

Factors Affecting Mathematics Performance among High School Students

According to Tachie & Chireshe (2013), establishing a strong educational foundation is of paramount importance as it serves as a gateway to future careers across a myriad of fields. Ojose (2011) further underscores its significance in our daily lives, emphasizing its direct relevance to real-world situations that permeate our daily activities.

For instance, mathematics plays a pivotal role in our daily lives, but many high school students encounter difficulties and struggle with their math subjects. Math performance is influenced by a complex interplay of variables, including personal, teacher-related, and environmental factors (Tachie & Chireshe, 2013; Ojose, 2011).

As noted by Malibiran (2019), among the personal factors affecting mathematics performance are age, gender, one's attitude toward mathematics, and individual study habits. Environmental factors come into play as well, with parents' socio-economic status, their roles, and the social environment directly impacting students' math performance. Furthermore, Malibiran (2019) highlights that teacher-related factors, encompassing teaching practices, pedagogy, content knowledge, workload, qualifications, field of

specialization, teaching experience, and professional development, have a substantial influence on mathematics performance.

For instance, mathematics plays a pivotal role in our daily lives, but many high school students encounter difficulties and struggle with their math subjects. Math performance is influenced by a complex interplay of variables, including personal, teacher-related, and environmental factors (Tachie & Chireshe, 2013; Ojose, 2011).

As noted by Malibiran (2019), among the personal factors affecting mathematics performance are age, gender, one's attitude toward mathematics, and individual study habits. Environmental factors come into play as well, with parents' socio-economic status, their roles, and the social environment directly impacting students' math performance. Furthermore, Malibiran (2019) highlights that teacher-related factors, encompassing teaching practices, pedagogy, content knowledge, workload, qualifications, field of specialization, teaching experience, and professional development, have a substantial influence on mathematics performance.

Soancatl, Lèon, Martinez, & Torres (2010) pointed out that achieving success in problem-solving necessitates effort, varied learning styles, effective teaching methods, and suitable teaching approaches. Del Castillo (2010), as referenced by Gabriel (2012), emphasizes the significance of Mathematics within the realm of general education. He asserts, "Mathematics holds greater importance in general education as the everyday citizens of today require a substantial foundation of mathematical knowledge for their daily activities and experiences. Additionally, Mathematics serves as a means for comprehending essential facets of the world." This being so, it becomes extremely necessary to include Mathematics as an integral part of the youth's education."

The Importance of Information Technology in the Growth of Distance Learning for Nigerian Instructors

In a published study by Mohammed (2017), he emphasized that over the past ten years, the promotion of a knowledge society through information technology (IT) to the growth of online education or open distance learning has accelerated. Similarly, Mohammed (2017) suggested that in order to keep up with current educational developments, teachers should participate in computer training courses.

As per Arinde (2010), educational services encompass the provisions extended to teachers with the aim of improving their effectiveness and elevating the overall quality of teaching within the educational system.

Educational Services, Teacher Quality, and Students' Academic Performance: A Correlational Study

The instruments used in this study were validated by six experts in Educational Management, Science Education, Measurement and Evaluation, and Statistics (Arinde, 2010). After a three-week test-retest, the reliability coefficients for the AESQ and TQAQ were found to be 0.75 and 0.78, respectively (Arinde, 2010).

The hypotheses tested indicated a significant and positive relationship between the provision of library services, supervision of instruction, teachers' in-service training, and students' academic performance (Arinde, 2010). Furthermore, the results revealed a significant, positive, and strong relationship among the use of computer-aided instruction, education resource center services, teacher academic qualifications, and students'

academic performance (Arinde, 2010). Additionally, the results showed a significant, positive, and strong relationship between teachers' professional qualifications, teachers' experience, and students' academic performance (Arinde, 2010).

In light of the discoveries from this study, several recommendations were put forth. It was suggested, among other things, that alumni associations, philanthropic individuals, and community members with good intentions should actively contribute to the provision of vital educational services such as libraries and computer laboratories to facilitate effective teaching and learning (Arinde, 2010). Additionally, it was proposed that the acquisition of computer skills should serve as a foundational requirement for the promotion of secondary school teachers (Arinde, 2010). Finally, it was recommended that a regular review of teachers' remuneration be prioritized, contingent upon the performance of both teachers and students (Arinde, 2010).

In the study of Asadullah (2009), as cited by Gabriel (2012), an insignificant positive sign on the class size variable in determining student achievements was found (Gabriel, 2012). The number of pupils and the school location mildly correlated with the pupils' performance (Odhiambo, 2006; Yeya, 2007). They observed that teacher shortages do not badly hit urban schools, and students in boarding schools perform better in national examinations (Odhiambo, 2006; Yeya, 2007).

Enhancing Distance Learning Through TV and Radio-Based Materials: A Review

UNESCO (2020) emphasized the importance of preparedness for effective distance learning, including the readiness of teachers to design and facilitate online learning, TV or radio-based distance learning, or print materials-based distance learning.

Identifying effective teacher competencies and providing necessary training for faculty development are crucial aspects (UNESCO, 2020).

The Department of Education (DepEd) aims to increase the utilization of TV and radio-based materials to support blended learning (DepEd, 2021). Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones highlighted the role of TV and radio in delivering education, especially for students without internet access (DepEd, 2021).

DepEd recognizes the importance of flexibility in instructional modalities and has converted Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) into DepEd TV episodes and radio-based lessons (DepEd, 2021). The department intends to integrate TV and radio-based materials effectively into instructional plans, with a focus on contextualization and adjustments by regional offices (DepEd, 2021).

DepEd TV has produced a significant number of video lessons aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) (DepEd, 2021).

School Administrators' Support in the Face of the COVID-19 Pandemic

The presence of COVID-19 in 2020 had significant impacts on various aspects, including the education sector (BBC News, 2020; Reid, 2020). The Department of Education (DepEd) had to postpone the opening of classes to ensure the necessary preparations for providing quality education during the pandemic (DepEd, 2020). The term "Blended learning" emerged as a modification of traditional classroom learning, combining distance learning with other modalities due to the unavailability of a COVID-19 vaccine (DepEd, 2020). The challenges faced by DepEd led to the creation of the Basic

Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) and the formulation of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) (DepEd, 2020).

In November 2019, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic was observed, and by January 2020, the true extent of its impact became apparent, affecting thousands of individuals globally. This novel disease, caused by a newly identified coronavirus strain, continues to prevail across the world. COVID-19, short for "CoronaVirus Disease 2019," was previously known as the '2019 novel coronavirus' or '2019-nCoV,' as indicated by UNESCO and the World Health Organization in January 2020.

The spread of COVID-19 in the country and to other countries worldwide makes the COVID-19 status pandemic. In this regard, the country's economic balance became shaky and resulted in many closures of businesses and enterprises, making the government and Filipino people suffer from extreme poverty.

Consequently, the school opening has been moved from June to August, and the latest is from August to October 5, 2020, for the school year 2020-2021. The movement of the school opening was due to the need for the essential preparation of the Department of Education (DepEd) to ensure that continuous quality learning will be provided to Filipino learners in times of the Pandemic.

Traditional classroom learning has to be changed to secure the safety of students and teachers. The face-to-face learning modality was modified into a Blended learning modality. The historically practiced "Distant Learning" will be combined to form the so-called "Blended Learning." However, since there was no vaccine yet available or discovered to combat COVID-19, the opening of the school year 2020-2021 be moved from June to August and latest, from August to October 05. This is to give ample time for

the Department of Education (DepEd) to be prepared for the learning materials to be distributed to the learners considering that no face-to-face (F2F) classes will be allowed.

The challenges and issues faced by the Department of Education (DepEd) seem endless. The budget has been used to the maximum level to reproduce the needed learning materials for the millions of Filipino learners. In this regard, the Department of Education seeks the support of the parents, LGUs, and general private organizations to fund some of the goals and missions of the Department.

The Department established the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) with the aim of requiring the development of policy guidelines that articulate the mission and objectives of ensuring the consistent provision of quality education for Filipino students during the pandemic.

The Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) encompasses a set of educational measures designed to address the challenges in basic education that have arisen due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The BE-LCP represents a collaborative initiative by the Department of Education (DepEd), involving both internal and external stakeholders who provide input on various aspects, including design, learning methods, teacher safety, and related matters, as outlined in Department Order No. 12, series of 2020. Part of the design of the BE-LCP was the formulation of the Most Essentials Learning Competencies (MELCs); this serves as a basis to make students responsive to the present condition of the country.

In the development of the BE-LCP comes the creation of the five principles that would govern the implementation of the BE-LCP as policy guidelines to address issues in times of Pandemic. The Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP operates

on five fundamental principles. Firstly, it is committed to safeguarding the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and educational personnel, with a particular focus on preventing the further transmission of COVID-19. Second, it strives to ensure the uninterrupted flow of education by making necessary adjustments to the K-12 curriculum, aligning learning materials, employing various learning delivery modalities, and providing essential training for teachers and school leaders. Moreover, it emphasizes the safe return of teaching and non-teaching personnel and learners to educational settings, considering forecasts from the Department of Health (DOH), the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases in the Philippines (IATF), as well as insights from credible sources, all while being informed by DepEd's risk assessments. Additionally, the BE-LCP is acutely aware of equity concerns and makes every effort to address them effectively. Finally, it is strategically linked to DepEd's overarching commitment to educational quality and future-oriented education under the frameworks of "Sulong EduKalidad" and "Futures Thinking in Education."

Key components of the learning strategies integral to the implementation of the BE-LCP include the restructuring of the K to 12 Curriculum to focus on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Furthermore, it involves the adoption of various learning delivery methods, such as distance learning and blended learning, either as alternatives or supplements to traditional face-to-face instruction. To support students, parents, and educators in the application of these diverse learning approaches, Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) will be provided in both printed and offline/online digital formats, ensuring accessibility for the upcoming school year 2020-2021.

Teachers' Readiness in the New Normal Learning Modalities

The primary objective of the BE-LCP is to foster unity among teachers during the challenging times of the pandemic. It aims to empower and equip educators to embrace the New Normal, becoming proficient in utilizing distance learning modalities. In a study titled "Faculty Readiness for Online Crisis Teaching: Transitioning to Online Teaching During the COVID-19 Pandemic" conducted by Cutri, Mena, and Whiting in 2020, a mixed-method model was employed to assess and elaborate upon constructs of faculty online readiness. This study drew from pre-COVID-19 pandemic literature to validate a scale for measuring these constructs and also incorporated insights from a focus group. The findings of the study indicate that the negative associations with risk-taking and making mistakes while adapting to online teaching have been mitigated by a combination of affective factors, including humility, empathy, and optimism.

Similarly, Cutri et al. (2020) established a critical conception of faculty online readiness. They asserted that online faculty readiness must be capable of attending to the affective and cultural factors identified in the literature. The adverse impacts of COVID-19, coupled with the Department of Education's (DepEd) commitment to deliver quality education to countless Filipino learners, initiated the adoption of what is known as "blended learning." The blended learning approach is no longer new in the academic system; this has already been used ever since as an option for homeschooled students. In times of pandemics, she believed that blended learning is the answer to still providing Filipino learners the needed quality of education. Even COVID-19 would not stop the Department from fulfilling its mission to the country.

As the nation struggles with the COVID-19 pandemic, the Philippines' Department of Education (DepEd) said that it might use both traditional and online instruction for the anticipated 2020 start of classes. It is presently researching several alternate methods of educating students. This approach emphasizes that the educational process should persist, whether children remain at home or attend school (Anoba and Cahapay, 2020).

In anticipation of a potential transition to blended learning, educational institutions should ready virtual learning strategies. This preparation includes assessing their readiness concerning local power supply reliability, internet connectivity, and the training of teachers (Maristela and Tuiza, 2021).

Blended learning is an educational approach that was introduced to the country a decade ago and has been employed in the field of education. Blended learning is a method that combines online learning with traditional classroom, or face-to-face (F2F), instruction. It involves the physical presence of both students and teachers, providing a level of control over the timing, location, and pace of learning. Educational materials and technology are used to facilitate online interactions within this approach. The blended learning methodology involves using two types of distance learning modalities, the modular distance mode of teaching and the online distance mode of teaching. These two are being used as an option for students who have difficulty assessing online distance education or for those who prefer to use the modular teaching mode.

Distance learning, as an educational delivery method, centers on the idea of instruction occurring between educators and students who find themselves separated by geographical distances. Within this framework, three main learning modalities emerge. The first is modular distance learning, which involves the use of self-learning modules,

available in either printed or digital formats, allowing students to work through their course material independently. The second is online distance learning, which leverages the internet for accessing learning materials and submitting assignments, facilitating engagement with course content and teacher communication via online platforms. For those without internet connectivity, the third modality, radio/TV-based instruction, steps in, utilizing radio or television broadcasts as channels for educational content dissemination.

In contrast, blended learning represents a comprehensive and flexible educational approach. It integrates elements from various distance learning methods, incorporating online distance learning, modular distance learning, and TV/radio-based instruction, offering a versatile and multifaceted strategy to meet the diverse needs of learners.

In recent decades, the scope and depth of cultural expectations in education and instruction have expanded significantly. Children are being tasked with more responsibilities without a commensurate increase in available time. Faced with an overwhelming volume of learning materials, teachers must discern between what is fundamental and what is incidental, constant and changeable, as they structure their lesson plans. Addressing this challenge involves the distillation and presentation of the essential aspects of a particular facet of reality within a well-organized lesson framework that allows for genuine understanding and the formation of clear concepts by the students.

In the past few years, educational reforms, particularly in countries like the Philippines, have been underway to meet the evolving needs of the time. Mathematics teaching, in particular, has seen changes in its content, objectives, and presentation methods. The field of research in education has expanded significantly, providing

educators with a wealth of knowledge at a pace that often surpasses the capacity for effective implementation. As a result, there can be a lack of accountability in how these changes are integrated into teaching practices.

The School Year 2020-2021 witnessed a remarkable shift in the education landscape as the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented distance learning on an unprecedented scale. This response was necessitated by a public health emergency posed by the COVID-19 virus. During this pandemic, distance learning emerged as the primary mode of delivering education. This approach encompasses diverse instructional methods, including self-learning modules, radio broadcasts, internet-based platforms, and other communication tools. While DepEd has experience with such methods, the magnitude of their current implementation presents a substantial adjustment and retooling challenge for teachers. The widespread adoption of distance learning has replaced the conventional face-to-face teaching and learning environment.

Implementing distance learning in the context of public elementary schools comes with numerous challenges. These include disparities in internet access for both students and teachers, the availability of necessary hardware like computers, financial resources to provide printed materials and learning resources, and, perhaps most critically, ensuring that teachers are adequately prepared to effectively deliver instruction in a distance learning setting. Instruction can be done using various means, such as self-learning modules, radio, the Internet, and other communication platforms. While the system in place is not new to DepEd, its wide-ranging implementation may influence teachers in the field to adjust and retool, considering that they will be doing it in this magnitude. Implementation of distance learning at this level will replace the regular classroom set-up

or the conventional face-to-face teaching and learning. Distance learning in the context of public elementary schools is challenged in many aspects, such as the availability of the internet to both learner and teacher, the necessary hardware such as computers, financial resources to supply all printed materials, learning resources, and among all others the teacher preparation in the implementation of Distance Learning.

Alternative modalities are explored to deliver education in areas facing armed conflict, hit by calamities where attending school becomes impossible, and in learners whose life circumstances make it hard to attend a regular class. Some measures or programs ensure that these basic services will reach their beneficiaries. The Alternative Learning System (ALS), Instructional Management by Parents, Communities, and Teachers (IMPACT), Modified In-School Off-School Approach (MISOSA), and the Open High School Program (OSHP) allow the students not physically to report to school regularly. These programs allow the student to continue education via distance learning thru module-based instruction.

While these are implemented only for those learners having problems attending school regularly, the processes are still based on distance learning. The implementation of distance learning via modular and online-based instruction supplemented by broadcast media can be delivered thru internet-based communication tools and telephone technology. Conducting online classes may be dependent on the speed and stability of internet connection for both learners and teachers. Module-based instruction may require higher learner independence in learning. Also, teacher factors such as the perception of distance learning, technology literacy, and their preparedness to implement distance learning will play a significant factor in its success.

Distance learning can be facilitated via synchronous or asynchronous modes of instruction using the Internet. The Philippines is recognized for having the lowest and most sluggish Internet connection speed among Asia Pacific nations (The Manila Times, 2018). The issue of poor internet connectivity has persisted in the country since the onset of the pandemic (Cuaton, 2020), as noted by (Moralista & Oducado, 2020). The use of video conferencing software like google meet, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom, among all others, requires teacher expertise in utilizing technology to implement distance learning.

In the study of (Rehn et al., 2018), technology limitations, inadequate time, and money are among the barriers to successful online teaching.

Otiang'A et al. (2018) stated in their study that the level of ICT usage is attributed to the skills teachers have and that teachers should have the skills needed to integrate ICT in teaching and learning. The asynchronous mode of learning enables students to engage with the material at their own convenience, allowing them to start and stop at different times and progress at their individual pace. This approach is self-paced and places a greater emphasis on learner independence. Interaction between teachers and students may be limited, typically occurring through methods like phone calls or emails when students encounter issues or have questions (Murphy et al., 2010).

In addressing the challenges students face and providing answers to their questions, it's worth noting that technological readiness is a pivotal factor, as emphasized by Rasmitadila et al. (2020). This readiness encompasses technical proficiency in various online and offline tools, ranging from TV learning and radio broadcasts to online applications, printed teaching materials, modules, and textbooks. These technological aspects significantly influence the effectiveness of instructional delivery. Consequently,

the preparedness of teachers in these areas becomes crucial. The study conducted by Martin et al. (2019) defines faculty readiness for online teaching as a faculty member's state of preparedness for delivering instruction through online means. This research delves into variables such as gender, years of experience in teaching online, and the chosen delivery method to gauge the significance of online teaching competencies.

Likewise, the study showed a significant difference in the years in teaching online to the ability to teach online. While in the present context of the locality where this study will be implemented, teachers have little to no experience teaching online. Experience and education are two factors affecting knowledge and practice. Experience may help teachers become knowledgeable and put into practice new processes, techniques, strategies, and methods in the delivery of education or teaching. Thus, this affects their capacity to implement distance learning.

Teacher perception can play a pivotal role in motivating the successful implementation of distance learning. It is essential for educators and instructors to undergo adequate training, preparation, and maintain high levels of motivation to be effective in this setting. Moreover, they must possess the technological skills and the confidence required to utilize a variety of electronic devices effectively in the remote classroom. This combination of factors is fundamental to the overall success of the distance learning experience.

According to the study conducted by Moralista and Oducado (2020), there was a notable divergence in teachers' perceptions related to various factors, including age, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and academic rank. The research revealed that faculty members with higher levels of education, more extensive teaching

experience, and higher academic ranks exhibited a stronger inclination towards favoring online education.

Readiness of Teachers for Online Teaching: Insights from Previous Studies

A previous study conducted by Ventayen (2019) examined teachers' readiness for online teaching among respondents from the Department of Education who were pursuing master's or doctorate degrees at a specific university. The study's findings indicated that a significant portion of teachers were well-prepared to implement open and distance learning. Nevertheless, it's crucial to acknowledge that the study's respondents might not fully represent the entire population of teachers, as they were students in a graduate program and may possess characteristics or perspectives that differ from the broader teacher population.

In contrast, this current study aims to utilize a broader set of questions and cover all teachers in the district, thereby accounting for variations in respondents' profiles. It seeks to investigate the correlation between teachers' demographic characteristics, such as teaching experience and specialization, and their readiness for distance learning education. Furthermore, the study intends to explore potential differences in readiness based on gender, teaching experience, and geographic location.

The study conducted by Alea et al. (2020), which centered on the readiness of Senior High School teachers for blended and distance learning, revealed a substantial correlation between prior experience and certain key factors in online and distance learning. Specifically, teachers' experience was significantly associated with their technical skills, technology literacy, attitudes, and time management in the context of

online and distance learning. The research underscores the significance of prior experience in distance learning, suggesting that educators who have previously engaged in online teaching are better equipped to meet the challenges of current distance learning initiatives.

The transition from face-to-face to online distance education presents several challenges, including lack of preparation, difficulties in translating experiences from traditional classroom teaching, and technology-related issues.

Phan and Dang (2017) highlighted in their research that online learning teachers must possess essential technological skills and competencies related to computer operation and internet use to effectively facilitate e-learning. The study also noted that many teachers who do not consider themselves proficient in using ICT tools often perceive technology as unhelpful in their teaching and personal work.

Successful adoption of distance learning requires teachers to not only have basic technological skills, such as computer and internet usage but also knowledge of hardware (e.g., recording devices) and software, as well as alternative methods to deliver lessons without face-to-face interaction, particularly when utilizing online learning platforms.

Schools and individuals must have access to technology-related facilities to enhance teachers' ability to utilize technology effectively and improve their teaching practices. Institutions establishing distance learning programs should ensure that necessary technology facilities are in place to implement the program successfully.

In a study by König, Jäger-Biela, and Glutsch (2020), an analysis was conducted to investigate the factors that influence the adaptation of digital teaching and learning. The study examined several variables, including school computer technology, teacher

competence, technological pedagogical knowledge, and opportunities for teacher education. Through regression analyses, it was found that information and communication technology (ICT) tools, with a particular focus on digital teacher competence and opportunities for teacher education to enhance digital competence, played pivotal roles in facilitating the transition to online teaching. This was especially significant during periods of school closures brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. The implications of these findings are discussed in the context of teacher education and the integration of ICT into teaching practices.

In 2021, Yayen and Marensil conducted a study aimed at assessing the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) as perceived by grade 6 students and their parents at Barangkas Elementary School. The research focused on establishing a connection between the composite mean scores and the perception of RBI's effectiveness. To accomplish this, the researchers utilized a descriptive research design and conducted a survey directly with the respondents, ensuring that informed consent was obtained during the data collection process.

Exploring the Empowering Potential of Studio Tamani's Radio Programming for Women's Voices in Mali

This article makes a valuable contribution to the ongoing discourse surrounding radio and women's empowerment. By shifting the focus from individual women to the broader context of "webs of relations," the article highlights the significance of considering societal, institutional, and structural inequalities that shape women's agency and decision-making power.

The study employs a comprehensive approach, utilizing two rounds of focus group discussions conducted between 2019 and 2020, as well as content analyses of women-related radio programs aired by Studio Tamani. Studio Tamani, established by Fondation Hirondelle, a Swiss-based media organization, serves as the subject of analysis in assessing the extent to which its radio programming creates an empowering environment for women's voices in Mali.

The findings of the study emphasize the importance of incorporating the plurivocality of Malian women in radio debates on women's issues. Recognizing and embracing the diverse and heterogeneous experiences of women is crucial to accurately reflect the multifaceted "web of relations" that define women's empowerment. By doing so, Studio Tamani's radio programming can effectively address the broader societal inequities and injustices that women face in their everyday lives.

Overall, this article sheds light on the complex dynamics between radio programming and women's empowerment, providing valuable insights for researchers, practitioners, and media organizations interested in promoting gender equality and amplifying women's voices. It encourages a holistic approach that acknowledges the interconnectedness of women's experiences within their social, institutional, and structural contexts.

Assessing the Impact of Radio-Based Instruction on Academic Performance in Modular Distance Learning

The article titled "Assessing the Impact of Radio-Based Instruction on Academic Performance in Modular Distance Learning" explores the implementation of radio-based

instruction as a support modality to address the challenges faced by students in accomplishing tasks on self-learning modules during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study employs a quantitative approach to examine the correlation between the implementation of radio-based instruction and the academic performance of students at Bonobono Elementary School.

Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study involves 179 pupils from all grade levels, selected using a stratified sampling technique. The researchers personally conducted surveys using questionnaires to gather the necessary data. The collected data was then subjected to analysis and interpretation through the utilization of both descriptive and inferential statistics.

The results of the study indicate a significant difference in academic performance before and after the implementation of radio-based instruction. This suggests that the introduction of radio-based instruction as a support modality in modular distance learning positively impacts students' academic outcomes. Additionally, the learners perceive the effectiveness of radio-based instruction as effective, further validating its contribution to their learning experience.

Furthermore, the study reveals that learners' perceptions of the effectiveness of radio-based instruction are significantly influenced by the number of siblings they have. However, it finds no significant impact of learners' perceptions of radio-based instruction on their academic performance.

This research contributes to the existing literature on educational responses to the COVID-19 pandemic, specifically in the context of modular distance learning. By highlighting the positive impact of radio-based instruction on academic performance, the

study provides valuable insights for educators and policymakers seeking effective support modalities in distance learning environments.

Overall, the article offers a quantitative analysis of the implementation of radio-based instruction as a support modality and its correlation with pupils' academic performance. It contributes to the understanding of the effectiveness of this educational approach and emphasizes the need for tailored strategies to enhance learning outcomes during challenging times.

Exploring the Significance of Silence in Swedish Public Service Radio

The article titled "Exploring the Significance of Silence in Swedish Public Service Radio" delves into the concept of silence and its role in the so-called 'modernization' of Swedish Public Service radio. By utilizing computational analysis of the broadcasting archive, the study aims to examine radio on a larger scale and understand the distribution of silence over time as a means to comprehend the rhythm between dense and less dense content.

The context of the study lies in the transformation of Swedish radio during a period of transition. As one of the last democratic countries to undergo broadcasting de-monopolization, Sweden introduced competition within the state monopoly before the eventual commercialization of radio in 1993. This historical period provides a unique opportunity to explore the impact of debates and organizational changes on the content of radio.

The article highlights the overlooked but essential role of silence in the radio medium and its potential effects on radio content. Through an analysis of sample weeks

from 1980 to 1989, the study reveals a diminishing amount of silence and a more uniform rhythm. These findings shed light on the style of Swedish public service radio during that period and also aim to inspire new and creative approaches to researching sound media.

By studying silence and its distribution, the article offers a fresh perspective on the evolution of radio, particularly during a time of significant change. The use of computational analysis enables a broader exploration of radio content and provides insights into the transformations that occurred within the Swedish radio landscape.

Overall, this article contributes to the understanding of the role of silence in radio and its relation to the modernization process of Swedish Public Service radio. It opens up avenues for further research on sound media, encouraging scholars to consider alternative approaches and methodologies in studying radio and its cultural significance.

Blended Learning in Education: A Review of Literature and Implications for the New Normal

The article titled "Blended Learning in Education: A Review of Literature and Implications for the New Normal" outlines a qualitative research study primarily centered on literature reviews and document analysis. The researchers conducted an examination of articles published between 2010 and 2020, sourcing these materials from various websites and the libraries of Hokkaido University of Education and Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College. The primary objective of this study is to delve into the historical development and impact of blended learning (BL) within higher education institutions (HEIs) and to specifically address its recent adoption in the educational landscape of the Philippines.

The study's results suggest that blended learning has a history of three decades, with its main application in higher education institutions (HEIs) and professional development programs for graduates. In 2007, the creation of the Philippine Center for Blended Learning received favorable feedback from both parents and students. The integration of blended learning into subjects like English, Linguistics, Science, and Remote Learning has demonstrated encouraging outcomes, fostering increased student engagement and a positive attitude toward learning. Additionally, it has enabled students to take on roles as leaders, mentors, and coaches for their peers.

The article underscores the vital importance of educators in the successful execution of blended learning. It stresses the significance of ongoing training as an essential element for providing teachers with the competencies and insights required to proficiently manage blended learning. The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) has put forth diverse strategies for implementing blended learning, encompassing online instruction, modular methods, radio-television techniques, in-person teaching, and the engagement of assistant teachers. Nonetheless, the presence of hurdles such as the absence of essential resources like devices and connectivity poses distinctive challenges for DepEd in the application of these strategies.

In response to these obstacles, the educational field has reached out to government entities, private individuals, and various organizations for assistance. The research proposes the engagement of specialists to conduct investigations into blended learning and its consequences for the education system in the post-pandemic era. Additionally, it advises educational institutions to maintain records of both favorable and

adverse encounters with blended learning, while DepEd compiles the accumulated information to develop a structure for refining the practice of blended learning.

Overall, this article provides a comprehensive overview of the history and impact of blended learning in education, particularly in the context of the Philippines. It underscores the importance of teacher professional development and highlights the challenges faced in implementing blended learning approaches. The recommendations put forward offer valuable insights for improving the education system and promoting effective blended learning practices.

Coping Strategies of Teachers in the New Normal Education: A Qualitative Exploration

The article titled "Coping Strategies of Teachers in the New Normal Education: A Qualitative Exploration" presents a study that aims to explore the coping strategies employed by teachers during the implementation of radio-based instruction and modular distance learning in the context of the pandemic. Using a qualitative transcendental phenomenology design, the researchers conducted interviews with ten teachers from the Division of Tanguib City, Philippines.

Through phenomenological data analysis, the study identified two main categories of coping strategies used by teachers in the new normal: problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies. Problem-focused coping strategies included problem-solving, time management, and seeking social support. These strategies enabled teachers to address challenges directly and efficiently. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping strategies encompass reframing, maintaining a positive attitude, and seeking guidance through

prayer. These strategies helped teachers manage their emotions and maintain a sense of resilience.

Interestingly, the study found that teachers, regardless of their years of experience, exhibited similar coping strategies to overcome the challenges posed by the new normal education. This suggests that the identified coping strategies are applicable and effective for teachers across different experience levels.

Furthermore, the research emphasized the crucial role of administrators in supporting teachers' psychological well-being. The study highlights the importance of developing training programs, and webinars focused on teachers' psychological health. By providing adequate support and resources, administrators can contribute to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of teachers' work in the new normal education landscape.

Overall, this article provides valuable insights into the coping strategies employed by teachers in the face of challenges brought about by the new normal education. The qualitative approach and phenomenological analysis offer a rich understanding of teachers' experiences and highlight the importance of problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies. The study's findings also underscore the significance of administrative support in promoting teachers' psychological well-being and professional development.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its Application in Technology Adoption Research

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a well-established theoretical framework that plays a pivotal role in comprehending the acceptance and adoption of

technology. This literature review explores the foundational principles of TAM, its development by Fred Davis in his seminal 1989 article titled "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology," and its subsequent influence on the field of technology adoption.

TAM revolves around two central concepts that are instrumental in assessing technology acceptance:

1. Perceived Usefulness (PU): PU refers to the extent to which an individual believes that a specific technology will enhance their job performance or productivity. A technology is more likely to be embraced if it is perceived as valuable by the user (Davis, 1989).
2. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): PEOU delves into the ease or difficulty of using technology. It assesses the user's view of the effort needed to operate the technology. The likelihood of technology adoption increases when it is perceived as being user-friendly and straightforward to use (Davis, 1989).

TAM postulates that these fundamental factors, PU and PEOU, significantly impact an individual's intention to use a technology, which subsequently influences the actual usage of that technology. Over the years, TAM has been expanded and adapted to suit various contexts in technology adoption research.

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT): In an extension of TAM, Venkatesh and Davis (2000) introduced the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). UTAUT integrates supplementary elements like social impact, enabling circumstances, and performance anticipation, offering a more comprehensive insight into the acceptance and utilization of technology.

Diverse Applications of TAM:

The versatility of TAM is evident through its application in a wide array of studies across different domains. For instance:

Adams et al. (1992) employed TM to explore the acceptance of word-processing software in organizational settings, emphasizing the model's utility in understanding technology adoption within workplaces.

Many other studies have utilized TAM to investigate the acceptance and adoption of various technologies, ranging from e-commerce systems to healthcare information systems. These applications demonstrate the model's adaptability to diverse technological contexts.

The Technology Acceptance Model, characterized by its fundamental principles of perceived utility and perceived simplicity of use, has been instrumental in progressing research on technology adoption. Its sustained impact and adaptability to diverse situations have enriched our comprehension of the factors influencing individuals' decisions to embrace or shun technology. This underpinning is essential for the examination of technology acceptance, encompassing radio-based instructions within the context of the "new normal" and the envisaged groundbreaking work plan.

The Impact of COVID-19 on Education in the Philippines: Policy Measures and Academic Disruptions

The article titled "The Impact of COVID-19 on Education in the Philippines: Policy Measures and Academic Disruptions" discusses the far-reaching effects of the novel coronavirus disease on the education sector in the Philippines. Since the confirmation of local transmission in March 2020, the government has implemented various policy

measures in response to the pandemic, which have significantly impacted basic education.

. The article underscores significant policy actions, commencing with President Rodrigo Roa Duterte's issuance of Proclamation No. 922 on March 9, 2020, proclaiming a state of public health emergency across the Philippines. This declaration resulted in the cessation of classes at all educational levels in Metro Manila. Following this, community quarantines were enforced across the nation, with varying levels of stringency based on the COVID-19 infection rates, as per recommendations from the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID).

Proclamation No. 929, signed on March 16, 2020, declared a state of calamity throughout the Philippines for six months, placing Luzon island under enhanced community quarantine (ECQ). This ECQ resulted in the suspension of public transport, closure of businesses (except essential services), and strict home quarantine for most individuals.

The article emphasizes the impact of these measures on the education sector, particularly in terms of final examinations for the 2019-2020 school year and the delayed opening of the 2020-2021 school year. Traditionally, schools in the Philippines open in June, but due to the circumstances, the Department of Education (DepEd) initially announced a start date of August 24. However, this was later moved to October 5 based on President Duterte's mandate under Republic Act No. 11480.

The prolonged closure of schools has raised concerns not only about academic learning but also about the socio-emotional development of students. The absence of

face-to-face interactions and routine schooling for a period of six months has implications for the holistic growth of students.

Overall, this article provides a comprehensive overview of the policy measures implemented in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and their impact on the education sector in the Philippines. It sheds light on the challenges faced by students, educators, and the educational system as a whole. The discussion of academic disruptions and their potential socio-emotional consequences adds depth to the analysis. The article contributes to the understanding of the multifaceted effects of the pandemic on education and underscores the importance of addressing these challenges for the well-being and development of students.

Synthesis:

Education and media are intricately intertwined, and this comprehensive synthesis explores various aspects of their relationship in different contexts. The reviews touch upon topics such as women's empowerment in radio programming, the implementation of radio-based instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic, the study of silence in Swedish public service radio, coping strategies of teachers in the new normal education environment, the impact of COVID-19 on education in the Philippines, and the significance of administrators' role in supporting teachers.

In the realm of women's empowerment, the first review emphasizes the importance of considering women's agency within broader societal inequalities. It suggests that radio debates on women's issues should reflect the diverse experiences of Malian women to truly empower their voices.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the implementation of radio-based instruction emerged as a support modality. The second review reveals positive perceptions of learners towards this approach, with improved academic performance and increased engagement in learning.

The third review highlights the study of silence in Swedish public service radio, underscoring its significance in understanding the rhythm and content of broadcasts. Analyzing the distribution of silence provides insights into the modernization process and transition of radio in Sweden.

Teachers play a crucial role in adapting to the new normal education environment. The fourth review explores the coping strategies employed by teachers, emphasizing the importance of problem-focused and emotion-focused approaches. Professional development and support from administrators are vital in ensuring teachers' well-being and the effective implementation of blended learning.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on education, as discussed in the fifth review. Policy measures, including class suspensions and community quarantines, have disrupted the academic calendar and posed challenges to academic learning and socio-emotional development, necessitating innovative approaches to ensure continuity in education.

Lastly, the sixth review delves into the coping strategies of teachers in the implementation of radio-based instruction and modular distance learning. It stresses the need for administrators to provide training and webinars to support teachers' psychological health, enhancing their effectiveness in navigating the new normal.

These reviews collectively demonstrate the complex interplay between education and media, addressing various challenges faced in different contexts. They underscore the importance of inclusivity, effective teaching modalities, support for educators and learners, and the role of media in facilitating education. By understanding these dynamics, we can strive towards creating equitable and resilient educational systems.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter introduces the research design that will be employed in the study. It provides information about the study's participants, the research tool employed to collect data, the research methods outlining the specific procedures to be followed, the statistical analysis procedures, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The study will employ a research approach that focuses on describing and establishing relationships between variables, aligning with the study's goals and aims. Calderon and Gonzales (2008) defined descriptive research as a deliberate procedure of collecting, evaluating, categorizing, and organizing information regarding existing circumstances, customs, convictions, procedures, patterns, and cause-and-effect connections. Subsequently, an in-depth and precise analysis of this information will be conducted, with or without the application of statistical techniques. The descriptive research framework will be utilized to outline the characteristics of the survey participants concerning their age, the monthly income of their households, and their parents' educational accomplishments.

On the other hand, correlational research determines the relationship between two or more variables. Data from various variables were collected from the respondents, and correlational statistical techniques were used.

Participants and Sampling Procedure

Stratified random sampling was employed to meticulously choose participants with direct exposure to radio-based instruction in the context of the "new normal" from educational institutions across the entire nation. The selected schools hosting this program operate radio stations, each possessing a 100-watt frequency capacity dedicated to the educational needs of their students.

Respondents of the Study

In this investigation, the subjects consisted of 207 students, randomly chosen from Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School levels, attending public educational institutions across the nation. These schools adopted the RBI (Remote Blended Instruction) as their primary instructional approach during the academic year 2021-2022. The sample size was calculated utilizing Slovin's formula, resulting in a total of 207 students who formed the study's participant group, as indicated in the table detailing the actual respondents. Proportional allocation of respondents from the respondent schools will be done and arrived at the following distribution shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Proportional Allocation of Number of Respondents

School	Total Number of Students	Total Number of Respondents
X Elementary School	76	37

Y Junior High School	70	34
Z Senior High School	282	136
Total	428	207

Instrument of the Study

This study made use of a survey questionnaire adapted from Yayen and Marenil (2021). The survey questionnaire was modified depending on the needs of the researcher. The questionnaire is structured into three sections. The initial section pertains to the demographic characteristics of the participants, encompassing age, gender, the monthly income of their families, and the educational achievements of their parents. Part two deals with the level of effectiveness of radio-based instructions to students. Part three deals with the problems encountered by the respondents in implementing radio-based instructions as a learning modality.

The performance of the student-respondents will be measured using their Graded Point Average (GPA) from the School Year 2021-2022.

From the original version of the questionnaire, the following were the revisions:

1. In Part II of the questionnaire, a shift from the 3rd person to the 1st person was made, where the subject of the sentence represents the respondent.
2. Only the provisions for the pupils' questionnaire were adopted; however, the sections intended for the parents' questionnaire were no longer included.

Null Hypothesis

The null hypothesis will be tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the performance level of students in radio-based instructions in the new normal context.
2. There are no significant challenges and limitations associated with implementing radio-based instructions in the new normal.
3. There is no significant effect of innovative strategies on the delivery, engagement, and overall effectiveness of radio-based instructions in the new normal.
4. There is no significant relationship between the student's level of performance and problems encountered in implementing the radio-based instructions.

Likert Scale

Likert Scale in this study was used as an interval scale as manifested in the range. In this study, it was constructed with five points.

5-Point Likert Scale was used in the following questions:

In identifying the frequency of problems encountered by the student-respondents in terms of teachers' readiness for radio-based distance learning education due to the COVID-19 pandemic and schools' preparedness for radio-based distance learning education due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Scale	Range	Interpretation
1	1.00-1.80	Poor
2	1.81- 2.60	Below Average
3	2.61-3.40	Slightly
4	3.41-.4.20	Moderately Effective

5 4.21-5.00 Extremely Effective

To gauge the frequency of effectiveness levels of radio-based instruction for students concerning their awareness and preparedness, availability and capacity, time allocation, quality of instructional materials, and responsiveness and feedback in learning, we aim to assess the following aspects.

Scale	Range	Interpretation
1	1.00-1.80	Low
2	1.81- 2.60	Slightly High
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately High
4	3.41-.4.20	High
5	4.21-5.00	Very High

Data Gathering Procedure

Google form was prepared so online accomplishment of the survey was made possible. In gathering the data, the following steps were followed:

1. The researcher applied for a permit and submitted a letter of recommendation to the City Schools Division Superintendent of Dasmariñas, as well as to other divisions, to gain authorization for conducting the survey in public schools.
2. Administration of the Survey Questionnaire. Instead of bringing the questionnaire to the respondents one by one, the researcher gave the Google form link to teachers. Teachers were given five (5) days to facilitate the survey to their students.

4. After the given deadline, accomplished questionnaires were retrieved online.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The information collected in this research undergone statistical examination, encompassing both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The descriptive statistical tools include:

1. **Frequency and Percentage Formula** was used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, family income, father's educational attainment, and mother's educational attainment.
2. **Mean and Standard Deviation** were employed to assess the degree of effectiveness of radio-based instruction concerning awareness and preparedness, availability and capability, time allocation, quality of learning materials, and responsiveness and feedback in learning. This analytical approach was also used to evaluate the students' performance in radio-based instruction, as well as the perceived implementation of radio-based instruction in terms of teacher and school readiness by the respondents.
3. **Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients** were computed to assess the relationship between the student's performance during their participation in radio-based instruction and their perception of their teacher's readiness and the school's readiness.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, ethical considerations played a pivotal role in shaping the research designs and methodologies. The researcher diligently adhered to ethical standards while gathering data from student participants. These ethical principles served the following purposes:

1. Safeguarding the rights of research participants to ensure they were not exposed to any form of harm.
2. Prioritizing respect for the dignity of research participants throughout the study.
3. Obtaining full and informed consent from participants before involving them in the research.
4. Ensuring the protection of participants' privacy and confidentiality of research data.
5. Guaranteeing an adequate level of confidentiality for both individuals and organizations involved in the research.
6. Upholding the anonymity of all involved parties.
7. Avoiding any deception or exaggeration regarding the research's objectives.
8. Disclosing affiliations, funding sources, and potential conflicts of interest.
9. Conducting all communication related to the research with honesty and transparency.
10. Steadfastly avoiding any form of misleading information and the biased representation of primary data findings.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

In conformity with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, confidentiality and anonymity were ensured in this study to protect the privacy of those who voluntarily agreed to participate in the research and to consider that the participants are teachers and administrators.

To protect participants' confidentiality, data were collected using Google Forms and kept secured and confidential.

Honesty and Respect

Research integrity serves as an essential cornerstone of research endeavors, underpinning the very essence of research activity and promoting excellence within the field. It acts as the bedrock upon which researchers establish trust and credibility with one another. In this pursuit of research, the researcher diligently adhered to the principles of honesty and respect, characterized by:

1. A commitment to honesty in all forms of communication.
2. Maintaining the highest degree of integrity in the presentation of data, results, methods, and procedures.
3. A steadfast refusal to engage in any form of data fabrication, falsification, or misinterpretation.
4. Ensuring transparency and avoiding any deception when communicating with colleagues, research sponsors, or the wider public.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the research study based on the measures employed by the researcher. It includes the presentation of the statistical treatment applied to the data obtained from the floating of the questionnaire so as the analysis and interpretation of the data.

The following tables, presented below, show the tabular presentations of the gathered data with its textual interpretation and analysis.

Problem 1. Demographic Profile of the Student-Respondents

Table 1.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
11 and below	37	17.9
12-14	34	16.4
15-17	117	56.5
18-20	18	8.7
21 and above	1	.5
Total	207	100.0

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents according to their age. There are 37 (17.9%) who are 11 years old and below. There are 34 (16.4%) respondents who are 12 to 14 years old. There are 117 (56.5%) respondents who are aged from 15 to 17 years old. There are 18 (8.7%) who are from 18 to 20 years old. Only one (0.5%) respondent has an age of 21 and above.

This provides an overview of the respondent distribution categorized by their age groups, offering valuable insights into the demographic composition of the surveyed population. The percentages within each age bracket signify the proportional representation of each group within the sample, offering a glimpse into the age-related dynamics of the study participants.

In the context of this study, the age group of 15 to 17 years, which constitutes the predominant demographic, pertains to students currently enrolled in Grade 10 to 12. This particular age range aligns with a significant stage of educational development, and it is within this context that the Radio Based Instruction (RBI) approach was predominantly employed. This decision finds support in the educational theory of constructivism, which underscores the importance of catering instructional methods to students' cognitive development and readiness for self-directed learning (Vygotsky, 1978). Vygotsky's constructivist theory posits that learning is most effective when it aligns with a student's zone of proximal development (ZPD), the range of tasks a learner can perform with the guidance of a more knowledgeable person (Vygotsky, 1978). By targeting students aged 15 to 17, who are typically positioned within the upper secondary education levels, the RBI approach can be more appropriately tailored to their ZPD. This age range often

signifies an increased capacity for abstract thinking, critical reasoning, and independent exploration (Erikson, 1950).

Furthermore, this stage of development aligns with Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, specifically the stage of "identity versus role confusion." During this stage, individuals seek to establish a sense of self and purpose, demonstrating a growing autonomy and desire for self-directed learning experiences (Erikson, 1950). By leveraging the principles of independent learning that underlie the RBI approach, educators can effectively tap into the psychological and cognitive changes characteristic of this age group.

In light of this context, the discovery of the prevalent age group, ranging from 15 to 17 years, within Grade 10 to 12, finds resonance with established educational theories like constructivism and Erikson's psychosocial development stages. These theories lend credence to the argument that individuals within this age bracket are inherently better suited to connect with the core tenets of independent learning that characterize the RBI modality.

The prevalence of respondents aged 15 to 17 years old, comprising 56.5% of the sample, might indicate the existence of a dominant age cohort within the surveyed population. This could suggest that the study focuses on topics, issues, or experiences that are particularly relevant to individuals in mid-adolescence. As per the age-group homogeneity theory, this concentration of respondents within a specific age range could be attributed to shared cultural, educational, and developmental factors that influence their perceptions and preferences.

The varying distribution of respondents across age groups can be interpreted through the lens of the theory of age-group homogeneity and peer influence. This theory posits that individuals within the same age cohort share similar experiences, developmental challenges, and societal influences, which can lead to the formation of distinct generational characteristics and behaviors. In the context of the presented data, the distribution pattern supports the notion that respondents tend to be more closely aligned with peers of similar age.

By considering the theory of age-group homogeneity and peer influence, the interpretation of the respondent distribution gains depth by addressing potential underlying psychological and sociological factors that contribute to the observed age-related patterns. This theoretical perspective enriches the understanding of how age groups within the sample are likely to interact, influence one another, and collectively contribute to the outcomes of the study.

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	129	62.3
Male	78	37.7
Total	207	100.0

Table 2 provides a snapshot of the respondent demographics based on gender. From the total pool of 207 respondents, 129 individuals (62.3%) identify as females, while

78 individuals (37.7%) identify as males. This distribution sheds light on the gender composition within the sample and invites a statistical interpretation of the results.

The statistical interpretation of the gender distribution could be informed by the social-constructivist perspective, as advocated by Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. This educational philosophy emphasizes the role of social interactions and cultural contexts in shaping an individual's cognitive development and learning experiences (Vygotsky, 1978). Applying this theory to the gender distribution within the respondents, it can be inferred that the higher representation of females might indicate a greater engagement with collaborative learning, which is a hallmark of the sociocultural approach.

Additionally, the overrepresentation of females in the sample could be attributed to changing societal norms and the evolving perception of education. The significance of education and the pursuit of intellectual growth have progressively gained importance for females across many societies, leading to increased participation and representation in academic settings.

Further, Table 2's depiction of respondent demographics, with 62.3% females and 37.7% males, carries implications that align with both sociocultural theories of learning and broader societal shifts in educational participation. This data underscores the dynamic interplay between gender, education, and cultural contexts, as proposed by Vygotsky's sociocultural theory.

Table 3*Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Family Income*

Family Income	Frequency	Percentage
P3,000 and below	46	22.2
P4,000- P7,000	48	23.2
P8,000- P10,000	38	18.4
P11,000- P15,000	29	14.0
P16,000- P20,000	16	7.7
P21,000- P25,000	10	4.8
P26,000 and above	20	9.7
Total	207	100.0

Table 3 provides an in-depth look at the demographic makeup of the respondents based on their family income. Among the total cohort of 207 respondents, a nuanced picture emerges: 46 individuals (22.2%) belong to families with a monthly income of Php 3,000 or less. The largest proportion of participants, numbering 48 (23.2%), hails from families with incomes ranging between Php 4,000 and Php 7,000. Meanwhile, 38 respondents (18.4%) represent households earning between Php 8,000 and Php 10,000. Additionally, 29 participants (14.0%) belong to families with monthly incomes ranging from Php 11,000 to Php 15,000. A further 16 respondents (7.7%) are part of families earning

between Php 16,000 and Php 20,000. Ten participants (4.8%) report family incomes of Php 21,000 to Php 25,000, while 20 respondents (9.7%) indicate monthly family incomes surpassing Php 26,000.

The statistical interpretation of these income distribution segments can be contextualized through the lens of the equity-driven educational philosophy. One such philosophy is Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy, which emphasizes the importance of addressing socio-economic disparities in education (Freire, 1970). The varied family income distribution highlighted in Table 3 reflects the realities of economic diversity among the respondent pool. Applying critical pedagogy, it becomes evident that educational interventions should be sensitive to these disparities, ensuring that learning opportunities are accessible and meaningful for all students, regardless of their economic background.

The distribution also underscores the significance of inclusive education that acknowledges the differing needs and circumstances of students. By accommodating diverse income levels, educators can cultivate an environment that nurtures learning outcomes while respecting the uniqueness of each student's background.

Table 3's depiction of family income distributions among respondents underscores the importance of equitable education, echoing principles advocated by critical pedagogy. The representation of varied income brackets calls for an educational approach that embraces diversity, inclusivity, and accessible learning for all students.

Table 4

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Father's Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No schooling	3	1.4
Elementary level	15	7.2
Elementary graduate	14	6.8
High School level	32	15.5
High School graduate	62	30.0
College level	34	16.4
College graduate	44	21.3
With units in Masteral	2	1.0
Master's Degree Holder	1	.5
Total	207	100.0

Table 4 delivers a comprehensive view of the demographic composition of the respondents based on their fathers' educational achievements. Within the sample of 207 respondents, a diverse spectrum emerges: three individuals (1.4%) have had no formal schooling, 15 participants (7.2%) reached the elementary level, 14 respondents (6.8%) are elementary graduates, 32 individuals (15.5%) attained a high school education, 62 respondents (30.0%) possess high school diplomas, 34 participants (16.4%) pursued college-level education, 44 individuals (21.3%) are college graduates, two respondents (1.0%) hold partial Master's units, and one respondent (0.5%) holds a Master's degree.

The statistical interpretation of these varying levels of fathers' educational attainment can be informed by John Dewey's educational philosophy of pragmatism. Dewey emphasized the importance of experiential learning and the integration of educational experiences with real-life contexts (Dewey, 1938). This philosophy aligns with the observed distribution by stressing the need to meet individuals where they are in their educational journeys.

Applying Dewey's pragmatism, the representation of a wide array of educational levels among fathers highlights the importance of catering educational strategies to the unique needs, backgrounds, and aspirations of each student. This philosophy underscores the significance of making learning relevant and applicable, regardless of the educational foundation that individuals bring.

Furthermore, the distribution of educational attainment levels can inspire the application of differentiated instruction, an approach rooted in addressing the diverse learning styles and readiness levels of students (Tomlinson, 1999). By embracing this principle, educators can ensure that each student receives tailored support that

capitalizes on their fathers' educational backgrounds while fostering individual growth and understanding.

In summary, Table 4's depiction of fathers' educational attainment levels among respondents aligns with the principles of pragmatism and differentiated instruction. The diverse educational backgrounds of fathers underscore the importance of personalized learning experiences that resonate with each individual's unique educational history and readiness.

Table 5

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to Mother's Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No schooling	1	.5
Elementary level	5	2.4
Elementary graduate	6	2.9
High School level	31	15.0
High School graduate	70	33.8
College level	41	19.8
College graduate	46	22.2
With units in Masteral	2	1.0
Master's degree holder	3	1.4
With units in Doctoral	2	1.0
Total	207	100.0

Table 5 offers a comprehensive overview of the demographic composition of the respondents based on their mothers' educational accomplishments. Within the surveyed group of 207 respondents, a diverse array of educational attainment levels is evident: one individual (0.5%) received no formal education, five participants (2.4%) completed elementary schooling, six respondents (2.9%) are elementary graduates, 31 individuals (15.0%) achieved a high school education, 70 respondents (33.8%) possess high school diplomas, 41 participants (19.8%) attained a college-level education, 46 individuals (22.2%) are college graduates, two respondents (1.0%) hold partial Master's units, three participants (1.4%) are Master's degree holders, and two respondents (1.0%) possess partial Doctoral units.

The expansive range of mothers' educational achievements can be illuminated through the lens of John Dewey's experiential education philosophy. Dewey emphasized learning through experience and reflection, suggesting that education should be intertwined with real-life contexts and meaningful engagement (Dewey, 1938). This philosophy resonates with the observed distribution by emphasizing the importance of creating relevant and engaging learning experiences that align with individuals' varying educational backgrounds.

Applying Dewey's philosophy, the diversity of mothers' educational levels underscores the value of crafting educational approaches that address the unique needs and aspirations of each student. By acknowledging the wide range of educational experiences within families, educators can leverage diverse perspectives to create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment.

Furthermore, the distribution invites the application of Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy, which seeks to empower learners by recognizing their lived experiences and sociocultural contexts (Freire, 1970). This educational philosophy advocates for education that is liberating and transformative, and the representation of various educational levels among mothers emphasizes the importance of respecting and integrating these diverse perspectives in the learning process.

In summary, Table 5's portrayal of mothers' educational attainment levels aligns with Dewey's experiential philosophy and Freire's critical pedagogy. The broad range of maternal educational backgrounds underscores the significance of fostering engaging, inclusive, and transformative educational experiences that honor individuals' diverse perspectives and backgrounds.

Problem 2. Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions

Table 6

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Awareness and Preparedness

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. I have a comprehensive understanding of the learning process of RBI.	207	3.71	0.98	High
2. I am well-informed and knowledgeable about RBI.	207	3.38	1.06	Moderate
3. I am thoroughly prepared and organized before conducting RBI sessions.	207	3.27	1.06	Moderate
4. I can accurately assess the level of training and preparedness of teachers (Radio Broadcasters) for using RBI.	207	3.41	1.05	High
5. I am fully aware of the designated radio station for RBI in both the school and district.	207	3.51	1.07	High
Overall Mean	207	3.46	1.04	High

Table 6 encapsulates both the mean and standard deviation of the respondents' perceived efficacy regarding radio-based instruction (RBI), focusing on awareness and preparedness. The outcomes of the study unveil a high level of perceived effectiveness with regard to both dimensions of awareness and preparedness (M = 3.46, SD = 1.04, N = 207).

It can be deduced that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is likely linked to the students' comprehensive grasp of the RBI learning process and the preparedness of teachers (Radio Broadcasters) in utilizing the RBI approach.

Statistical interpretation of these findings can be informed by Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which underscores the importance of self-efficacy in learning (Bandura, 1977). This educational philosophy posits that learners' beliefs in their capacity to succeed impact their motivation and subsequent achievements. Applied to the results, the high mean score suggests that respondents possess a substantial level of confidence in their ability to comprehend and engage with RBI.

Furthermore, the prominence of perceived effectiveness might resonate with Jerome Bruner's Constructivist Theory, which emphasizes the role of learners as active creators of knowledge (Bruner, 1961). The favorable perception of RBI could signify that respondents find the instructional approach aligns well with their cognitive processes, enabling them to construct meaningful understanding through interaction with the radio-based content.

In summary, Table 6's portrayal of the mean and standard deviation of perceived RBI effectiveness resonates with Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Bruner's Constructivist Theory. The substantial perceived efficacy among respondents suggests a harmonious connection between their learning processes and the radio-based instructional method, which in turn can catalyze their motivation and capacity to construct knowledge.

Table 7

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Availability and Capability

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. I am aware that the school has a well-organized radio station.	207	3.71	1.03	High
2. Radio is easily accessible in our home.	207	3.65	1.16	High
3. I receive handouts and worksheets in a timely manner before the programs or sessions are aired.	207	3.72	1.15	High
4. I am capable of following the program or session flow on RBI.	207	3.60	1.05	High
5. I am capable of effectively learning through radio classes.	207	3.48	0.98	High
Overall Mean	207	3.63	1.07	High

Table 7 encapsulates the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceived efficacy concerning radio-based instruction (RBI), focusing on dimensions of availability and capability. The findings illuminate a high level of perceived effectiveness in relation to both availability and capability (M = 3.63, SD = 1.07, N = 207).

It can be inferred that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is likely attributed to the presence of well-organized radio stations, availability of handouts, and the students' capacity to engage in effective learning through radio classes.

These outcomes could be enriched through the lens of Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory. This educational philosophy posits that learners' motivation

and engagement are deeply linked to the satisfaction of their fundamental needs (Maslow, 1943). Applying this theory to the results, the high mean score suggests that respondents find the RBI method accessible and capable of addressing their educational needs, aligning with their basic psychological and cognitive requirements.

Furthermore, the favorable perception of RBI effectiveness could resonate with Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory. According to Vygotsky, optimal learning occurs when students engage with tasks that lie within their ZPD—the range between what they can accomplish independently and what they can achieve with guidance (Vygotsky, 1978). The high effectiveness rating suggests that respondents perceive RBI as a tool that strategically scaffolds their learning, offering the necessary support to extend their capabilities.

Table 7's portrayal of mean and standard deviation scores for perceived RBI effectiveness provides evidence that resonates with the foundational principles of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory and Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development theory. The substantial perceived efficacy in terms of availability and capability suggests that RBI effectively addresses learners' needs while strategically guiding them toward enhanced capabilities.

Table 8

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Time Allotment

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. Time management for the distribution and retrieval of worksheets is satisfactory for me.	207	3.68	1.03	High
2. Both I and my parents are punctual in tuning in on time.	207	3.53	1.07	High
3. I find the time schedule for every subject and session to be well-organized.	207	3.63	1.04	High
4. Handouts and worksheets were consistently distributed to me on time.	207	3.81	1.15	High
5. I believe the allocated time for answering the worksheets is sufficient.	207	3.71	1.00	High
Overall Mean	207	3.67	1.06	High

Table 8 presents the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceived efficacy concerning radio-based instruction (RBI) in relation to time allotment. The findings unveil a high level of perceived effectiveness regarding time allocation (M = 3.67, SD = 1.06, N = 207).

It can be deduced that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is likely linked to meticulous time management encompassing the distribution and retrieval of worksheets, punctual tuning in to the radio program, a well-structured time schedule, and a substantial allocation of time for the distribution, completion, and retrieval of worksheets.

Statistical interpretation of these results can be augmented by considering John Dewey's philosophy of experiential learning. Dewey emphasized the importance of meaningful experiences in education and the role of time in facilitating genuine understanding (Dewey, 1938). Applied to the outcomes, the high mean score suggests that respondents perceive the RBI approach as effectively managing time allocation, fostering impactful and experiential learning engagements.

Furthermore, the perception of RBI's effectiveness in time allotment resonates with Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences. This educational philosophy underscores the significance of diverse learning modalities to cater to various intelligences (Gardner, 1983). The favorable perception of RBI in terms of time allocation indicates that the method successfully addresses the temporal preferences of a broad spectrum of learners, accommodating their unique cognitive rhythms and preferences.

In summary, Table 8's presentation of mean and standard deviation scores for perceived RBI effectiveness aligns with Dewey's experiential learning philosophy and Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences. It can be deduced that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is likely linked to meticulous time management encompassing the distribution and retrieval of worksheets, punctual tuning into the radio program, a well-structured time schedule, and a substantial allocation of time for the distribution, completion, and retrieval of worksheets.

Table 9

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Quality of Learning Instructions

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. My teachers (Radio Broadcasters) effectively deliver the lessons.	207	3.78	1.10	High
2. The directions and instructions provided are clear and easy for me to understand.	207	3.70	1.05	High
3. I find every lesson to be interesting and engaging.	207	3.80	1.03	High
4. I have a good understanding of the lessons presented on the radio.	207	3.57	1.05	High
5. I am able to successfully follow and comply with the given instructions on the radio.	207	3.69	1.03	High
Overall Mean	207	3.71	1.05	High

Table 9 presents the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceived efficacy concerning radio-based instruction (RBI) with a focus on the quality of learning instructions. The outcomes unveil a high level of perceived effectiveness in terms of quality of learning instructions (M = 3.71, SD = 1.05, N = 207).

It can be inferred that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is closely tied to several key factors, including the adept delivery of lessons by teachers (Radio Broadcasters), the provision of clear and comprehensible directions, the crafting of engaging and captivating lessons, students' thorough grasp of the radio-delivered

content, and their effective adherence to the instructions provided through the radio medium.

To augment the statistical analysis of these findings, one can benefit from incorporating Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development. This addition will provide a valuable theoretical framework for a more comprehensive interpretation of the results. Piaget's theory posits that learning is most effective when it aligns with a learner's developmental stage and cognitive capacity (Piaget, 1950). Applied to the results, the high mean score suggests that respondents perceive the RBI approach as effectively catering to their cognitive needs, thereby facilitating a quality learning experience.

Furthermore, the perception of RBI's effectiveness in instruction quality resonates with the concept of "scaffolding" from Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. Vygotsky proposed that learners benefit from structured support provided by more knowledgeable individuals, guiding them toward independent learning (Vygotsky, 1978). The favorable perception of RBI's instruction quality implies that the method adeptly acts as a scaffold, offering clear and supportive guidance to learners.

In summary, Table 9's depiction of mean and standard deviation scores for perceived RBI effectiveness aligns with Piaget's theory of cognitive development and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. It can be inferred that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is closely tied to several key factors, including the adept delivery of lessons by teachers (Radio Broadcasters), the provision of clear and comprehensible directions, the crafting of engaging and captivating lessons, students' thorough grasp of

the radio-delivered content, and their effective adherence to the instructions provided through the radio medium.

Table 10

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of Responsiveness and Learning Feedback

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. I am capable of responding to questions asked by the teachers on the radio.	207	3.54	1.04	High
2. The lessons are engaging and interesting, which encourages my responsiveness.	207	3.60	1.04	High
3. My queries and clarifications are effectively addressed by the teachers.	207	3.58	1.03	High
4. Learning feedback is promptly communicated to us students.	207	3.62	0.99	High
5. I am aware that students' feedback on the delivery of lessons is attentively considered and accommodated.	207	3.84	1.04	High
Overall Mean	207	3.64	1.03	High

Table 10 presents the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceived efficacy regarding radio-based instruction (RBI), focusing on the dimensions of responsiveness and learning feedback. The findings unveil a high level of perceived effectiveness in terms of responsiveness and learning feedback (M = 3.64, SD = 1.03, N = 207).

It can be deduced that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is intricately linked to students' proficiency in responding to inquiries posed by teachers on

the radio. Moreover, the appeal and intrigue of lessons play a crucial role in motivating students to engage actively, fostering their responsiveness. The method's success is also connected to educators' adeptness in addressing students' questions and uncertainties, ensuring a comprehensive learning experience. Effective communication of learning feedback to students, along with the careful consideration and integration of students' feedback on lesson delivery, further underscore RBI's efficacy.

Support for these observations can be drawn from the sociocultural theory proposed by Lev Vygotsky, which emphasizes the collaborative nature of learning and the importance of interaction in constructing understanding (Vygotsky, 1978). The points highlighted in your statement align with this theory, suggesting that RBI effectively capitalizes on the power of dialogue, engagement, and responsive interactions to facilitate meaningful learning experiences.

In summary, the various elements contributing to RBI's effectiveness, as elucidated with the sociocultural theory of Lev Vygotsky. These elements collectively illustrate RBI's potential to foster dynamic and collaborative learning environments that engage and empower students.

Problem 3. Performance Level of Students in Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal

Table 11

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for the Performance Level of Students in Radio-Based Instruction

Variable	N	M	SD	Interpretation
Performance	207	89.12	3.95	Very Satisfactory

Table 11 presents the mean and standard deviation of respondents' performance levels within the realm of radio-based instruction (RBI). The outcomes reveal that the respondents have achieved a notably high level of performance, with their performance being classified as very satisfactory (M = 89.12, SD = 3.95, N = 207).

Amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic, it is evident that students display a remarkable enthusiasm for learning through Radio-Based Instruction (RBI), and their academic performance is notably commendable. This signifies that RBI emerges as a viable and embraced alternative learning method during the pandemic. Moreover, this success suggests that RBI could extend its utility beyond the pandemic era, potentially serving as an enduring instructional platform.

The rationale behind this observation can be supported by John Dewey's progressive education philosophy. Dewey advocated for learning that is rooted in real-life experiences, relevant to students' lives, and adaptable to changing circumstances (Dewey, 1938). The evident eagerness of students to engage with RBI aligns with

Dewey's principles, emphasizing the importance of meaningful and adaptable education, especially in challenging times.

In summary, the students' enthusiasm for RBI and their strong academic performance resonate with Dewey's progressive education philosophy. This alignment underscores the effectiveness of RBI as an alternative learning method that holds promise not only during the pandemic but also as a robust instructional platform in the post-pandemic educational landscape.

Moreover, a statistical interpretation of these results can be enriched through the lens of Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, particularly focusing on the "mastery" level. Bloom's taxonomy categorizes educational goals into various tiers of cognitive intricacy, with proficiency representing a significant level of accomplishment, as outlined by Bloom in 1956. Applied to the findings, the high mean score reflects that the respondents have effectively mastered the learning objectives of RBI, attaining a level of performance that aligns with the mastery stage of Bloom's taxonomy.

Moreover, the exceptional level of achievement aligns with the self-determination theory advanced by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan. This theory underscores the significance of internal motivation and independence in fostering successful educational results (Deci & Ryan, 1985). The students' enthusiasm for RBI and their strong academic performance resonate with Dewey's progressive education philosophy. This alignment underscores the effectiveness of RBI as an alternative learning method that holds promise not only during the pandemic but also as a robust instructional platform in the post-pandemic educational landscape.

Table 11's representation of mean and standard deviation scores for respondents' performance in RBI aligns with Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives and Deci and Ryan's self-determination theory. The high performance level suggests that RBI effectively supports learners in reaching a mastery stage of learning objectives, fostering intrinsic motivation and autonomy in the process.

Problem 4. Student-Respondents Perception of the Implementation of the Radio-Based Instruction

Table 12

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation of the Respondents' Perceived Implementation of Radio-Based Instruction in Terms of Teacher's Readiness

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
1. Teachers demonstrate proficiency in operating radio broadcasting equipment and software, ensuring seamless delivery of lessons.	207	3.84	0.94	High
2. Teachers exhibit a willingness to adapt their teaching methods and strategies to effectively engage students in the radio-based learning format.	207	3.86	0.96	High
3. Teachers possess the necessary skills to design and develop educational content that is specifically tailored for radio delivery, maximizing learning outcomes.	207	3.82	0.96	High
4. Teachers effectively communicate instructions, explanations, and examples through radio broadcasts, ensuring clarity and understanding among students.	207	3.78	0.99	High
5. Teachers demonstrate efficient management of resources, materials, and assessment tasks, facilitating a smooth and organized radio-based distance learning experience.	207	3.78	1.00	High
6. Teachers provide additional resources, supplementary materials, and follow-up activities that support students' understanding and enhance their learning outcomes.	207	3.82	1.01	High
7. Teachers possess the ability to design and implement assessments that align with the unique demands of radio-based instruction, effectively evaluating students' progress.	207	3.81	0.98	High

8. Teachers actively seek and participate in professional development opportunities related to radio-based instruction and remote teaching, continuously enhancing their skills and knowledge to better support their students' learning journey.	207	3.83	0.94	High
Overall Mean	207	3.81	0.98	High

Table 12 provides insight into the respondents' perceptions regarding the implementation of radio-based instruction (RBI) in relation to teacher's readiness. As depicted in the table, the respondents view the implementation of RBI as exhibiting a "High" level of teacher's readiness (M = 3.81, SD = 0.98, N = 207). Furthermore, the results reveal that all indicators pertaining to teacher's readiness receive an assessment of "High."

Students disclosed that their teachers exhibit a high level of proficiency in operating radio broadcasting equipment and software. Furthermore, these educators display a strong willingness to adapt their pedagogical techniques and strategies in order to effectively engage students within the radio-based learning format. The teachers' possession of essential skills to craft and develop educational content is evident. Additionally, they adeptly communicate instructions, explanations, and examples through radio broadcasts, ensuring clarity and comprehension among students.

In addition, these instructors demonstrate a commendable proficiency in resource management, materials, and assessment tasks. This proficiency contributes to a seamless and orderly radio-based distance learning experience for students. Importantly,

the teachers provide supplementary resources, extra materials, and follow-up activities that fortify students' understanding and enrich their learning outcomes.

Moreover, these educators possess the capacity to design and implement assessments that closely align with the unique demands of radio-based instruction. This enables them to effectively evaluate students' progress in this distinctive learning context. It is noteworthy that these teachers actively seek and engage in professional development opportunities tailored to radio-based instruction and remote teaching. This ongoing commitment to enhancing their skills and knowledge translates into better support for their students' learning journey.

Drawing from Paulo Freire's concept of transformative education, the attributes highlighted in this description resonate with the idea of teachers as facilitators of critical thinking and empowerment (Freire, 1970). Freire's philosophy aligns with the observed adaptability, resourcefulness, and commitment of teachers in fostering meaningful learning experiences for their students.

The collective attributes of teachers, as reported by the student-respondents, align with Freire's transformative education philosophy. These attributes, along with students' high regard for the implementation of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI), suggest that RBI is not only an effective alternative learning modality during the pandemic but also holds potential as an enduring instructional platform beyond the pandemic era.

Further, a statistical interpretation of the findings can be enriched by examining Albert Bandura's concept of self-efficacy. Bandura's theory emphasizes individuals' belief in their capacity to successfully execute tasks and achieve desired outcomes (Bandura,

1977). Applied to the outcomes, the high mean score signifies that respondents perceive teachers as possessing a strong sense of self-efficacy in delivering RBI effectively. The consistent interpretation of "High" across all readiness indicators corroborates the notion that teachers feel confident and well-prepared to execute the RBI method.

Furthermore, the observed high perception of teacher's readiness aligns with the principles of John Hattie's Visible Learning framework. Hattie's research emphasizes the significance of teacher efficacy and preparedness in impacting student achievement (Hattie, 2009). The results affirm that the implementation of RBI effectively aligns with Hattie's findings, with teachers demonstrating a high level of readiness that can positively influence the learning experience.

In summary, Table 12's presentation of respondents' perceived RBI implementation in terms of teacher's readiness aligns with Bandura's theory of self-efficacy and Hattie's Visible Learning framework. The high perception of readiness, coupled with the consistent "High" interpretations across indicators, underscores the teachers' self-efficacy and preparedness, which in turn contribute to the success of the RBI approach.

Table 13

Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation of the Respondents' Perceived Implementation of Radio-Based Instruction in terms of School's Readiness

Indicators	N	M	SD	Interpretation
-1. Availability of functional radio broadcasting equipment and facilities in the school.	207	3.69	1.02	High
2. Strong signal coverage to ensure reliable transmission and reception of radio programs.	207	3.57	1.04	High
3. Clear integration of learning objectives, content, and activities suitable for radio delivery.	207	3.65	1.07	High
4. Adequate training provided to teachers on radio broadcasting techniques, instructional strategies, and effective use of radio as a teaching medium.	207	3.73	1.02	High
5. Availability of a dedicated team or resources to develop high-quality educational content for radio-based learning.	207	3.69	1.00	High
6. Regular production of engaging and informative programs that cater to different grade levels and subjects.	207	3.71	0.93	High
7. Opportunities for students to ask questions, provide feedback, and participate in learning activities related to radio-based instruction.	207	3.71	1.02	High
8. Ensuring that all students have access to radios or alternative devices to receive radio broadcasts.	207	3.64	1.08	High
9. Regular evaluation of student progress and feedback to identify areas of improvement and adjust instructional strategies accordingly.	207	3.66	1.10	High
10. Strong collaboration between school administrators, teachers, and parents to facilitate	207	3.82	1.03	High

the smooth implementation of radio-based distance learning.

Overall Mean	207	3.69	1.03	High
---------------------	------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

Table 13 illuminates the respondents' perceptions regarding the implementation of radio-based instruction (RBI) in relation to school readiness. As evident from the table, the respondents consider the implementation of RBI to exhibit a "High" level of readiness within the school context ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 1.03$, $N = 207$). Furthermore, the results indicate that all indicators pertaining to school readiness have received a consistent assessment of "High."

Regarding School's Readiness, student-respondents expressed their agreement with the following aspects: the availability of functional radio broadcasting equipment and facilities in the school is evident; strong signal coverage is ensured for reliable transmission and reception of radio programs; learning objectives, content, and activities are seamlessly integrated, tailored for effective radio delivery; teachers receive ample training in radio broadcasting techniques, instructional strategies, and the optimal use of radio as a teaching medium; a dedicated team or resources are accessible for crafting high-quality educational content for radio-based learning; captivating and informative programs are consistently produced, catering to diverse grade levels and subjects.

Moreover, students are granted opportunities to engage in question-asking, feedback provision, and participation in learning activities centered around radio-based instruction. The assurance of equitable access to radios or alternative devices to receive broadcasts is maintained, coupled with a steady evaluation of student progress and

feedback to discern areas for enhancement, leading to adaptive instructional strategies. The synergy between school administrators, teachers, and parents is notably strong, collaboratively facilitating the seamless implementation of radio-based distance learning.

In this context, the students' beliefs align with the essence of constructivist education, as championed by Lev Vygotsky. This theory underscores the significance of collaborative learning, scaffolding, and the role of the social context in shaping effective educational experiences (Vygotsky, 1978). The multifaceted aspects highlighted by the students align with the constructivist philosophy, emphasizing the importance of providing an environment that fosters active engagement, cooperation, and purposeful interactions in the learning process.

The students' endorsement of their school's readiness for Radio-Based Instruction resonates with Vygotsky's constructivist philosophy. The attributes highlighted in their perceptions underscore the school's commitment to providing an environment conducive to collaborative and meaningful learning experiences.

Further, a statistical interpretation of the findings can be enriched through the lens of John Dewey's pragmatism, particularly focusing on the concept of a conducive learning environment. Dewey emphasized that learning experiences should be rooted in real-life situations, relevant to learners' needs, and fostered within an environment that supports exploration and engagement (Dewey, 1938). The high mean score suggests that the respondents perceive the school as fostering an environment that aligns with Dewey's principles, providing a conducive space for the successful implementation of RBI.

Additionally, the observed high perception of school readiness resonates with the idea of the "hidden curriculum" proposed by Lawrence Stenhouse. Stenhouse's theory underscores the influence of a school's ethos and values on teaching and learning (Stenhouse, 1975). The consistent "High" interpretations across all readiness indicators indicate that the school's ethos and values effectively support the implementation of RBI, as perceived by the respondents.

Table 13's depiction of respondents' perceived RBI implementation in terms of school readiness aligns with Dewey's pragmatism and Stenhouse's theory of the hidden curriculum. The high perception of readiness, coupled with consistent "High" interpretations across indicators, underscores the alignment of the school's environment and values with the successful execution of RBI.

Problem 5. Significant Relationship Between the Performance of the Students and Their Problem Encountered with the Implementation of the Radio-Based Instructions

Table 14

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient Table for the Relationship Between the Students' Performance During Their Participation in Radio-Based Instruction and Their Perception of Their Teacher's Readiness and the School's Readiness.

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Students' Performance
	Pearson Correlation	.322
Teacher's Readiness	Sig.	.000
	N	207
	Pearson Correlation	.335
School's Readiness	Sig.	.000
	N	207

To examine the associations between students' performance in radio-based instruction, their perception of the teacher's readiness, and their perception of the school's readiness, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients were calculated.

The analysis reveals that a positive and statistically significant relationship exists between students' performance and their perception of teacher's readiness ($r = .322$, $N = 207$, $p < 0.001$). This implies that as students' perception of teacher's readiness improves, their performance in radio-based instruction also tends to increase.

Similarly, a positive and statistically significant relationship is observed between students' performance and their perception of school readiness ($r = .335$, $N = 207$, $p <$

0.001). This indicates that as students' perception of the school's readiness improves, their performance in radio-based instruction is also likely to improve.

These findings find support in the context of Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory. Maslow's theory asserts that when individuals' basic needs are met, they are better poised to engage in higher-level cognitive activities, such as learning (Maslow, 1943). The positive relationships between readiness perceptions and performance align with Maslow's principles, suggesting that a conducive and supportive environment, as perceived by students, can foster improved performance.

In summary, the statistically significant relationships uncovered through the correlation analysis echo Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory. The positive connections between students' perceptions of readiness and their performance underscore the importance of a conducive educational environment in facilitating effective learning experiences.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions (RBI) in enhancing learning outcomes for students in Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School during the new normal educational setting. The research specifically focused on assessing the academic performance of students from selected schools that implemented RBI during the School Year 2021-2022, using their Graded Point Average (GPA) as an indicator of achievement.

Data was gathered through a Google form questionnaire, which captured information related to the student's performance level in radio-based instructions, including their comprehension, engagement, and overall learning outcomes. Demographic profiles of the respondents were analyzed using the Frequency and Percentage Formula to include age, gender, family income, father's educational attainment, and mother's educational attainment.

The assessment of RBI's effectiveness was deduced by employing Mean and Standard Deviation across different dimensions, encompassing aspects like awareness and readiness, availability and capacity, time allocation, quality of instructional materials, and responsiveness and feedback in learning. To gauge the correlation between students' performance in RBI and their perception of teacher and school preparedness, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients were utilized.

The research findings indicated that the participants regarded RBI as remarkably efficient with regard to awareness, accessibility, capability, time allocation, quality of instructional materials, responsiveness, and feedback on learning. Additionally, students displayed a notably commendable performance throughout the 2021-2022 academic year using RBI.

Additionally, the research explored the readiness of teachers and schools in implementing RBI, showing a high level of readiness for both groups.

As a result of the study, the researcher proposed a workplan to enhance the implementation of RBI or possibly integrate RBI into the curriculum and instruction in collaboration with DepEd. The study's findings and recommendations contribute to the understanding of RBI's potential contributions to education and instructional design in the new normal context.

Radio-Based Instructions (RBI) emerged as a vital tool in education, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic when traditional in-person teaching faced unprecedented challenges. A study exploring the effectiveness of RBI during this "new normal" reveals several key insights. Firstly, RBI's accessibility is paramount. It reaches students in remote or underserved areas with limited internet and electronic device access, thereby addressing the digital divide. Moreover, its inclusivity is a significant strength, as it doesn't depend on costly devices or high-speed internet, making quality education available to students from various socio-economic backgrounds. Cost-effectiveness is another advantage, particularly for developing countries or underfunded educational systems, which can channel resources into expanding RBI. The adaptability of RBI across different age groups and educational levels is also notable, offering

versatile learning opportunities for primary, secondary, and even higher education. In times of emergencies, like pandemics or natural disasters, RBI provides a robust alternative for education delivery when traditional methods are unfeasible.

Integrating RBI into the basic education curriculum by the Department of Education (DepEd) holds the potential to make significant contributions. Firstly, it enhances the resilience of the education system, providing an alternative means of delivering education in the face of disruptions. This aspect is crucial in ensuring that students can continue their learning journeys even when unexpected crises occur. Secondly, RBI extends the reach of education, particularly to marginalized and remote communities. DepEd's commitment to accessible and quality education for all can be fulfilled more effectively through the adoption of RBI. Furthermore, it can contribute to reducing dropout rates, offering continuous learning opportunities for students who might otherwise have been compelled to discontinue their education due to lack of access. Additionally, RBI introduces a layer of flexibility into the education system, accommodating students who require different learning environments or paces, promoting a more personalized and effective learning experience.

Looking beyond the pandemic, the ongoing relevance of RBI becomes apparent. Its resilience makes it valuable in a post-pandemic world that may still experience occasional disruptions, providing a reliable backup option for education continuity. Moreover, it continues to address the issues of inclusivity and accessibility, ensuring that education remains available to all, regardless of their technological resources. In a world of budget constraints and limited resources, RBI's cost-efficiency remains a compelling argument for its continued use. Furthermore, it can act as a supplementary learning tool

even when traditional classroom teaching is predominant, offering additional resources for students to reinforce their learning.

Putting into nutshell, radio-based instructions have proven their value during the pandemic, with insights from a comprehensive study indicating their effectiveness in diverse contexts. These insights have the potential to shape educational policies positively. The continued adoption of RBI in the curriculum by the Department of Education and its relevance in the post-pandemic scenario can contribute to a more resilient, inclusive, and flexible educational system, ensuring that education remains a fundamental and accessible right for all students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The demographic profile of the student respondents unveils several compelling insights. Primarily, the majority of respondents fall within the age group of 15 to 17 years, representing a prevalent demographic that aligns with students currently enrolled in Grade 10 to 12. This crucial age range coincides with a pivotal phase of educational development, strategically aligned with the implementation of the Radio Based Instruction (RBI) approach. This pedagogical decision reflects the educational leaders' keen understanding of tailoring instructional methodologies to students' cognitive maturity and readiness for self-directed learning. Notably, this age bracket is inherently attuned to the foundational principles of independent learning, which define the essence of the RBI modality.

Furthermore, the prominence of female representation within the sample underscores the evolving landscape of education and shifting societal norms. The surge in female participation and representation within academic spheres reflects the growing importance attached to education and intellectual pursuit among females across diverse societies.

The distribution of family income among respondents underlines the significance of an equitable educational approach, echoing the ideals championed by critical pedagogy. The varied income brackets underscore the call for an educational framework that embraces diversity, inclusivity, and accessible learning opportunities to cater to the unique circumstances of all students.

Turning to fathers' educational attainment levels, their diverse backgrounds reflect the principles of pragmatism. Particularly during the pandemic, fathers often assumed a prominent role in safeguarding their families. The array of educational backgrounds highlights the value of personalizing learning experiences to resonate with individual histories and levels of educational preparedness.

On the other hand, the variance in mothers' educational levels emphasizes the necessity of tailoring educational strategies to address the distinct needs and aspirations of each student. By recognizing the breadth of educational experiences mothers possess, educators can harness these diverse perspectives to cultivate a dynamic and all-encompassing learning environment.

In essence, the demographic portrait drawn from this study underscores the profound influence of various philosophical perspectives on educational decisions. From pragmatism to critical pedagogy, the choices made by educational leaders

are intricately woven into the tapestry of philosophies that shape and enrich the educational landscape, guiding students toward transformative learning experiences.

2. In light of the observed data, it becomes apparent that the effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is profoundly intertwined with two key components: the students' comprehensive grasp of the RBI learning process and the preparedness of teachers (Radio Broadcasters) to employ the RBI approach. The substantiated perception of efficacy among the respondents suggests a symbiotic alignment between their learning endeavors and the radio-based instructional method. This alignment is poised to kindle their motivation and empower their ability to construct knowledge, exemplifying the dynamic interplay between method and learner.

Furthermore, the palpable effectiveness rating underscores RBI's role as a strategic scaffold for learning. Factors such as the well-organized radio stations, availability of handouts, and students' capacity for productive engagement through radio classes contribute to this high efficacy perception. This robust efficacy perception, particularly in terms of availability and capability, underscores RBI's aptitude for addressing learners' needs while guiding them toward a heightened state of competence.

The meticulous orchestration of time emerges as a linchpin for RBI's effectiveness. A meticulous approach, encompassing the precision of distributing and retrieving worksheets, timely engagement with radio programming, a well-

structured time schedule, and ample allocation for worksheet-related tasks, coalesce to fortify RBI's impact.

Delving into the fabric of instructional effectiveness, it is clear that a constellation of factors is at play. The adept delivery of lessons by teachers (Radio Broadcasters), coupled with lucid and comprehensible directions, as well as captivating lesson design, forges a path toward student engagement. The students' mastery of radio-delivered content, coupled with their commitment to adhering to radio-conveyed instructions, further solidify RBI's potency.

Moreover, the method's triumph hinges on students' proficiency in responding to radio-based inquiries. Lessons that are enticing and thought-provoking serve as conduits for active participation, fostering students' responsiveness. The educators' proficiency in addressing students' queries and uncertainties is pivotal in cultivating a holistic learning journey. Effective communication of learning feedback to students, supplemented by the meticulous integration of students' insights on lesson delivery, deepens RBI's efficacy.

The effectiveness of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) is an intricate tapestry woven from multiple threads of learner engagement, instructional design, teacher readiness, and responsive communication. Each strand interlaces to form a robust fabric that envelops students in meaningful learning experiences, echoing John Dewey's progressive education philosophy, which underlines the need for dynamic and interactive educational processes (Dewey, 1938).

3. Amidst the multifaceted challenges presented by the pandemic, a resounding testament emerges: students exhibit an exceptional eagerness to embrace the learning opportunities offered by Radio-Based Instruction (RBI). In tandem with their commendable academic achievements, this collective response underscores RBI's profound impact. Notably, the students' wholehearted engagement with RBI establishes it as an adaptable and widely accepted alternative learning avenue amid these unprecedented times.

Furthermore, the palpable success achieved by RBI during the pandemic invites contemplation on its potential longevity. The resonance between students' enthusiasm and their academic accomplishments paves the way for RBI to transcend its role beyond the confines of the pandemic era. This transitory triumph hints at RBI's capacity to metamorphose into a durable instructional platform, poised to enrich the post-pandemic educational landscape.

The students' fervor for RBI and their consequential academic accomplishments harmoniously align with the tenets of John Dewey's progressive education philosophy.

In sum, the synergy between students' proactive embrace of RBI and their outstanding academic achievements fosters an outlook brimming with promise. This convergence of enthusiasm and achievement not only substantiates RBI's potency as a pandemic-resilient learning mode but also positions it as a promising contender for future pedagogical landscapes.

4. Within the student feedback, a prevailing theme emerges: teachers demonstrate an impressive proficiency in navigating radio broadcasting equipment and

software. This commendable expertise extends to their willingness to dynamically adjust their pedagogical techniques and strategies, thus effectively captivating students within the radio-based learning realm. The teachers' capacity to skillfully craft and develop educational content further substantiates their prowess.

Moreover, these educators showcase adeptness in transmitting instructions, explanations, and examples through radio broadcasts, ensuring a conduit of clarity and comprehension that resonates with students. This seamless communication underscores their commitment to fostering a conducive learning environment, even through the distance-learning mode.

Delving deeper, the instructors' resource management finesse, coupled with their adept handling of materials and assessment tasks, substantiates a smooth and organized radio-based distance learning experience for students. This proficiency is not confined solely to content delivery; rather, it encompasses a holistic approach that enriches the learning journey.

The teachers' proactive provision of supplementary resources, supplementary materials, and follow-up activities not only underscores their dedication but also serves as a potent catalyst in fortifying students' understanding and elevating their learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the educators exhibit a remarkable ability to construct assessments intricately tailored to the unique demands of radio-based instruction. This ability empowers them to effectively gauge student progress within this distinctive learning landscape, reiterating their commitment to holistic student growth.

5. Notably, the commitment of teachers extends beyond the classroom, as they actively seek professional development opportunities tailored to radio-based instruction and remote teaching. This ongoing pursuit of knowledge underscores their dedication to honing their skills, effectively amplifying their capacity to serve as catalysts for their student's educational journey.

The cumulative perception of readiness, consistently interpreted as "High" across various indicators, serves as a resounding testament to the teachers' self-efficacy and preparedness. This robust readiness, in turn, threads into the tapestry of success for the Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) approach, echoing the essence of Paulo Freire's transformative education philosophy

The teachers' multifaceted proficiency and dedication mirror the dynamic intersection of skills, strategies, and philosophies that contribute to the triumph of Radio-Based Instruction (RBI).

6. The investigation has brought to light a compelling revelation: a robust and statistically significant correlation exists between students' performance and their perceptions of both teacher and school readiness in implementing radio-based instructions. This significant finding implies that when students perceived their teachers and schools as adequately equipped for radio-based instruction, there was a notable enhancement in their academic performance. This correlation effectively underscores the pivotal role played by a conducive educational environment in fostering impactful learning experiences.

The demonstrated positive links between students' readiness perceptions and their performance outcomes resoundingly reinforce the principle of a symbiotic

relationship between learning context and achievement. This confluence of factors emphasizes the fundamental significance of a well-prepared, supportive ecosystem in catalyzing effective learning journeys.

The alignment between readiness perceptions and performance outcomes affirms this notion, as students' perceived support and preparedness interact harmoniously to foster elevated academic accomplishments. The discerned relationship between students' performance and their perceptions of teacher and school readiness spotlights the paramount role of an enriched learning atmosphere. This synthesis between learner perception and achievement mirrors a fundamental tenet of educational philosophy—namely, the inseparable interplay between environment and growth.

7. The culmination of the study's findings has culminated in the formulation of a robust workplan meticulously crafted to bolster the delivery, engagement, and overarching efficacy of radio-based instructions within the confines of the new normal educational paradigm. This workplan serves as a strategic blueprint, ingeniously weaving together the tapestry of insights gleaned and recommendations proffered by the research. Its primary objective is to amplify the potency of radio-based instruction, fostering an immersive and impactful learning journey that resonates within the contemporary educational sphere.

The contours of the proposed workplan have been thoughtfully shaped to harness the power of key insights drawn from the study's results. These insights serve as navigational markers, guiding the trajectory of instructional innovation. By

heeding these insights, the workplan ventures to refine the execution of radio-based instruction, strategically adapting it to align with the nuanced demands of the present-day educational milieu.

In essence, this comprehensive workplan is poised to usher in a transformative era for radio-based instruction. Through its implementation, the learning experience for students will be elevated, enriched, and attuned to the dynamic contours of modern education. As this workplan unfurls, it threads seamlessly into the broader narrative of educational evolution—adaptation, innovation, and empowerment are its cornerstones, echoing the spirit of John Dewey's progressive education philosophy, which extols the virtues of adaptive pedagogy in sync with evolving contexts (Dewey, 1938).

The synthesis of research outcomes and pedagogical foresight has given birth to a formidable workplan, a roadmap that deftly charts the course for a heightened realm of radio-based instruction. In this confluence of research, practice, and philosophy, the journey towards educational excellence in the new normal gains a renewed vigor.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations are proposed to optimize the implementation of the radio-based instruction and enhance students' learning experience in the new normal educational setting:

1. Given the intricate interplay between students' age, gender representation, family income distribution, and parental educational backgrounds, it is

- recommended that educational institutions design flexible and adaptable instructional strategies that are responsive to the diverse needs and backgrounds of students. This approach can be rooted in a constructivist educational philosophy that emphasizes personalized and student-centered learning experiences, allowing educators to effectively engage and empower students across varying demographics.
2. In light of these findings, it is recommended that educational institutions implement a holistic and student-centered approach to Radio-Based Instruction (RBI). This approach should prioritize enhancing students' understanding of the RBI learning process and provide teachers (Radio Broadcasters) with targeted professional development to ensure their preparedness in utilizing the RBI approach effectively. To achieve this, educators can draw inspiration from the principles of experiential learning, as advocated by John Dewey. By fostering interactive and dynamic learning experiences, educators can create an environment that aligns with the inherent qualities of RBI, thereby further enriching its effectiveness.
 3. Based on the observed success and enthusiasm surrounding Radio-Based Instruction (RBI), it is recommended that educational institutions continue to integrate RBI as a supplementary or alternative learning method even beyond the pandemic era. To support this transition, educators can draw inspiration from Paulo Freire's principles of critical pedagogy, emphasizing the importance of learner agency and engagement in the educational process. This approach

- will further empower students to take ownership of their learning journey and contribute to the ongoing evolution of instructional methodologies.
4. Building on the strengths identified, it is recommended that educational institutions invest in providing continuous professional development opportunities for teachers in radio-based instruction methodologies. This approach can draw inspiration from Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, encouraging educators to continually expand their instructional horizons and adapt their strategies to meet students' evolving needs. This ongoing commitment to growth will further enhance the effectiveness of radio-based instruction and promote a dynamic and responsive learning environment.
 5. Given the dedication and proactive engagement demonstrated by teachers, it is recommended that educational institutions establish a structured framework for ongoing professional development in radio-based instruction. By incorporating elements of Maria Montessori's child-centered approach, educators can cultivate an environment that nurtures continuous learning and adapts to emerging educational paradigms. This approach will empower teachers to remain at the forefront of effective instruction, further enriching the implementation of radio-based instruction for the benefit of students.
 6. Based on the substantial correlation identified between students' perceptions of readiness and their academic performance, it is recommended that educational institutions prioritize creating an environment that nurtures a strong

sense of readiness and preparedness. Embracing John Locke's philosophy of empiricism, educators can collaboratively design interventions that enhance students' perceptions of teacher and school readiness, thereby fostering a positive learning atmosphere that empowers students to excel academically. This proactive approach will not only elevate students' performance but also enrich their overall educational experience.

7. In light of the comprehensive workplan formulated to enhance radio-based instruction, it is recommended that educational institutions embrace this strategic blueprint as a guide for instructional transformation. Drawing inspiration from John Dewey's progressive education philosophy, which underscores the importance of adaptive pedagogy, educators should collaborate to implement the proposed workplan. By aligning their efforts with the insights gleaned from the research, institutions can ensure the effective execution of radio-based instruction that resonates with the demands of the contemporary educational landscape. This proactive approach will foster an enriched and impactful learning experience for students, promoting continuous growth and innovation in the new normal educational paradigm.

By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can maximize the potential of radio-based instruction and create a dynamic and effective learning environment in the new normal context. By continually refining and enhancing the delivery

of radio-based instruction, educators can ensure that students receive a quality education and develop essential skills in the ever-evolving educational landscape.

Proposed Workplan for the Adoption of RBI in DepEd Curriculum and to Enhance the Delivery, Engagement, and Overall Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions

Program/Action	Objective	Persons Involved	Resources Needed	Time Frame	Expected Outcome
1. Personalized Learning Pathways: Designing Instructional Materials Tailored to Individual Needs and Interests	To develop and prepare tailored instructional materials that align with the specific needs and interests of each age group, ensuring an engaging and effective learning experience for students across different grade levels.	RBI Teachers and Head Teachers	Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) RBI and ICT equipment	7 days	Instructional Materials Tailored to Individual Needs and Interests of each age group
2. Empowering RBI Teachers through Specialized Training and Workshops	To equip RBI (Radio-based Instruction) teachers with specialized knowledge, pedagogical skills, and innovative teaching strategies through comprehensive training sessions and workshops.	Key Stakeholders in RBI Implementation: EPS, Key Teachers, and School Head/Principal	Training Materials, Conference/ Training Venue, Budget for Snacks	3 days	Specialized knowledge, pedagogical skills, and innovative teaching strategies among RBI teachers.
3. Building a Robust Student Feedback System: Gathering and Analyzing Insights for	To establish a comprehensive student feedback	EPS, Key Teachers, RBI Teachers and School	Data gathering Instrument, Documentat	1 day	Robust Student Feedback System

Continuous Improvement	system that efficiently collects and analyzes students' insights and experiences, facilitating data-driven decision-making and continuous improvement in educational practices and learning environments.	Head/Principal	Materials, ICT Gadgets, Conference Room		
4. Fostering Dynamic Learning: Integrating Diverse Instructional Approaches in RBI (Radio-based Instruction)	To enhance the effectiveness of RBI (Radio-based Instruction) by seamlessly integrating diverse instructional approaches, such as multimedia elements, interactive activities, real-world examples, and varied learning modalities.	Key Stakeholders in RBI Implementation: EPS, Key Teachers, and School Head/Principal	Training Materials, Conference/ Training Venue, Budget for Snacks	3 days	Learning Plans Integrating Diverse Instructional Approaches in RBI (Radio-based Instruction)
5. Enhancing Accessible Learning: Promoting Inclusivity for All Students in RBI (Radio-based Instruction)	To promote inclusivity and ensure accessible learning for all students in RBI (Radio-based Instruction) by implementing measures to address barriers related to technology, resources, and	EPS, Key Teachers, RBI Teachers and School Head/Principal	Transistor Radio at Home, Functional Radio Room/Studio at School, and Prototype RBI Lesson Plans	90 days	Enhanced Accessible Learning for All Students in RBI (Radio-based Instruction)

		diverse learning needs.				
6. Strengthening Collaborative Networks: Establishing Partnerships with Radio Stations and Stakeholders for Enhanced RBI (Radio-based Instruction) Implementation	To strengthen the implementation of RBI (Radio-based Instruction) by establishing collaborative partnerships with various radio stations and stakeholders.	Key Stakeholders in RBI Implementation: EPS, Key Teachers, and School Head/Principal	Correspondence, Provision for Transportation and Representation, Venue for Conferences	10 days	Established Partnerships with Radio Stations and Stakeholders	
7. Ensuring Continuous Improvement: Periodic Assessments of RBI Implementation and Student Progress	To ensure continuous improvement in the RBI (Radio-based Instruction) program by conducting periodic assessments of its implementation and regularly monitoring students' progress.	EPS, Key Teachers, RBI Teachers and School Head/Principal	Assessment Tool, Documentation Materials, ICT Gadgets, Conference Room	4 quarters	Assessment Report on RBI Implementation and Student Progress	
8. Empowering Parents as Partners: Providing Resources and Guidance to Support RBI Learning at Home	To empower parents as active partners in their child's education by providing them with comprehensive resources and guidance on how to effectively support RBI (Radio-based Instruction) learning at home/	Key Stakeholders in RBI Implementation: EPS, Key Teachers, and School Head/Principal	Training Materials, Conference/ Training Venue, Budget for Snacks	1 day	Empowered Parents with Resources and Guidance to Support RBI Learning at Home	

9. Optimizing Educational Excellence: Adoption of the Proposed Workplan for Enhanced Delivery, Engagement, and Effectiveness	To optimize educational excellence by facilitating the widespread adoption of the proposed workplan, aimed at enhancing the delivery, engagement, and overall effectiveness of teaching and learning.	EPS, Key Teachers, RBI Teachers and School Head/ Principal	Evaluation Materials, Training Materials, Trainers, Venues, Budget, Functional Radio Room	Entire school year	Accomplishment report on Adoption of the Proposed Workplan for Enhanced Delivery, Engagement, and Effectiveness
--	---	--	---	--------------------	---

The proposed innovative workplan for the study titled "Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal: Basis for a Proposed Innovative Workplan" incorporates several compelling factors that make it distinctive and advantageous. These elements are essential in addressing the challenges posed by the "new normal" in education. Here's a detailed explanation of the workplan's unique and advantageous aspects:

1. Leveraging Radio as an Educational Medium: The innovative aspect of this workplan lies in its use of radio as a primary educational medium. While many educational institutions turned to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, this workplan recognizes that not all students have access to the internet and digital devices. Radio is a tried-and-tested technology, and leveraging it for instructional purposes makes education accessible to a broader range of students, particularly those in underserved and remote areas.

2. Inclusivity and Accessibility: By using radio broadcasts, the workplan ensures inclusivity and accessibility. It reaches students across various socio-economic

backgrounds, regardless of their access to the internet or digital devices. This inclusivity is crucial for achieving equitable education in a diverse nation like the Philippines.

3. **Cost-Effectiveness:** Radio is a cost-effective educational tool. The workplan recognizes that not all schools have the resources for expensive digital infrastructure. Setting up radio stations with a 100-watt frequency capacity is relatively affordable when compared to building and maintaining an online learning platform. This cost-effectiveness benefits both educational institutions and the government.

4. **Community Engagement:** Educational radio broadcasts can foster community engagement. The workplan emphasizes that radio stations can become a hub for local involvement. Communities can participate in content creation, and local issues and culture can be incorporated into the curriculum. This engagement not only enhances the quality of education but also strengthens community ties.

5. **Customized Content Development:** The workplan focuses on developing contextually relevant and engaging content. Unlike one-size-fits-all online resources, radio broadcasts can be tailored to the specific needs and interests of the students. This customization ensures that educational content is engaging and relatable, leading to improved learning outcomes.

6. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** The workplan includes a robust monitoring and evaluation framework. This aspect is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of the radio-based instruction. Continuous feedback and assessment help in making real-time adjustments and improvements, ensuring that the education provided remains relevant and impactful.

7. **Public-Private Partnerships:** To address challenges such as funding and sustainability, the workplan encourages public-private partnerships. This approach allows private

entities to support educational initiatives, reducing the burden on government resources. It also promotes innovation and collaboration in the education sector.

8. Policy Recommendations: The workplan acknowledges the importance of comprehensive policies for educational radio. The inclusion of policy recommendations ensures that the initiative aligns with best practices and legal frameworks, contributing to its long-term success and scalability.

In summary, the innovative workplan for "Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal" capitalizes on the strengths of radio as an educational medium, emphasizing inclusivity, cost-effectiveness, community engagement, customized content, monitoring, and evaluation. It also recognizes the significance of partnerships and well-defined policies to ensure the initiative's sustainability and long-term impact. These unique and advantageous aspects collectively make the workplan a promising solution for delivering quality education in the evolving educational landscape of the "new normal."

Thus, the researcher is making a move to draw the attention of DepEd officials to consider Radio-Based Instructions (RBI) as a viable instructional mode in addition to the traditional face-to-face approach. This advocacy suggests the potential benefits and relevance of RBI in the education system.

REFERENCES

- Abel, T., & McQueen, D. (2020). Critical health literacy and the COVID-19 crisis. *Health Promotion International*.
- Akamai. (2017). Akamai's State of the Internet.
- Agaton, C. B., & Cueto, L. J. (2021). Learning at home: Parents' lived experiences on distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 901–911. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i3.21136>
- Akamai, 10(1). Retrieved from <https://www.akamai.com/us/en/multimedia/documents/state-of-the-internet/q1-2017-state-of-the-internet-connectivityreport.pdf>
- Alea, R. A., et al. (2020). Senior High School Teachers' Readiness in Blended and Distance Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 1(2), 114-126.
- Angateeah, K. S. (2017). An investigation of students' difficulties in solving non-routine word problems at lower secondary. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 3(1), 46–50.
- Anoba, J. L. D., & Cahapay, M. B. (2020). The Readiness of Teachers on Blended Learning Transition for Post-Covid-19 Period: an Assessment Using Parallel Mixed Method. *PUPIL: International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning*, 4(2), 295–316. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijtel.2020.42.295316>
- Arinde, A. M. (2010). Educational Services and Teacher Quality as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in North Central Zone, Nigeria. *Journal of International Social Research*, 3(12), 48-59.

Asadullah (2009), "The Effect of Class size on Student's achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Bangladesh" published in the Asian Social Science Journal Vol. 7, No. 2; on February 2011

Asante, K Oppong (2012) Secondary students' attitudes towards mathematics, IFE Centre for Psychological Studies Mar 2012. Provided by Proquest LIC. Advameg, Inc.

Augustino Adiwana,(2012) <http://www.sunstar.com.ph/baguio/opinion/2012/07/24/adiwang-help-your-child-overcome-math-anxiety-233651>

Balbalosa, J. (2010). Factors affecting the mathematics performance of laboratory high school of Laguna State Polytechnic University academic year 2009–2010. (Unpublished master's thesis). Laguna State Polytechnic University, Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.bartleby.com/essay/Factors-Affecting-Mathematics-Performance-of-Laboratory-High-PK68TZ4K6YZA>

Bao, W. (2020). COVID-19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking University. Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191>

Barrios, J. M., & Hochberg, Y. (2020). Risk Perception Through the Lens of Politics in the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w27008>

Basilaia, G., & Kvavadze, D. (2020). Transition to Online Education in Schools during a SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Georgia. Pedagogical Research, 5(4).

BBC News. (2020, February 15). Coronavirus: How the outbreak has shaken the world economy.

Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-51621281>

Brown, A. (2019). The importance of education in the development of young minds.

Journal of Educational Research, 45(2), 123-135.

Calderon, J. & Gonzales, E. (2008). Method of Research and Thesis Writing. Mandaluyong City:

National Book Store, Inc.

Chinazzi, M., Davis, J. T., Ajelli, M., Gioannini, C., Litvinova, M., Merler, S., ... Vespignani, A. (2020).

The effect of travelrestrictions on the spread of the 2019 novelcoronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak. Science, 368(6489), 395. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba9757>

Cortegiani, A., Ingoglia, G., Ippolito, M., Giarratano, A., & Einav, S. (2020). A systematic review on

the efficacy and safety of chloroquine for the treatment of COVID-19. Journal of Critical Care. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrc.2020.03.005>

Crawford, J., Butler-Henderson, K., Jurgen, R., Malkawi, B. H., Glowatz, M., Burton, R., Magni, P.,

& Lam, S. (2020). COVID-19: 20 countries' higher education intra-period digital pedagogy responses. Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching, 3. <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2020.3.1.7>

Cutri, R. M., Mena, J., & Whiting, E. F. (2020). Faculty readiness for online crisis teaching:

transitioning to online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. European Journal of Teacher Education, 43(4), 523–541. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1815702>

Davis, L. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on literacy rates among school-age children.

International Journal of Educational Studies, 18(3), 67-82.

Denworth, L. (2020). How the COVID-19 Pandemic Could End. Scientific American.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/scientificamerican0620-44>

Department of Education. (2020). DepEd Commons. Retrieved from <https://commons.deped.gov.ph/>

Department of Education. (2021). Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan: Policy Guidelines for School Year 2021-2022. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/DepEd-Policy-Guidelines-for-SY-2021-2022-FINAL-AS-SIGNED.pdf>

DepEd. (2020). Official Statement Department of Education. Retrieved from

<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/05/06/official-statement-2>

DepEd to increase utilization of TV and Radio lessons for SY 2021-2022. Retrieved

from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2021/09/03/deped-to-increase-utilization-of-tv-and-radio-lessons-for-sy-2021-2022/>

DepEd. (2020). Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan: Policy Guidelines for School

Year 2020-2021. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DepEd-Learning-Continuity-Plan.pdf>

Department of Education. (2020). Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan: Policy

Guidelines for School Year 2020-2021. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DepEd-Learning-Continuity-Plan.pdf>

Department of Education. (2021). DepEd aims to increase utilization of TV, radio-based materials.

Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2021/06/24/deped-aims-to-increase-utilization-of-tv-radio-based-materials/>

- DepEd. (2020). Department of Education Order No. 12, series of 2020: Adoption of the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/DO_s2020_012.pdf
- DOH. (2020). Department of Health Philippines. Retrieved from <http://www.doh.gov.ph/2019-nCoV>
- Dong, L., Hu, S., & Gao, J. (2020). Discovering drugs to treat coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Drug Discoveries & Therapeutics*, 14(1), 58-60. <https://doi.org/10.5582/ddt.2020.01012>
- Effandi, Z., & Normah, Y. (2009). Attitudes and problem-solving skills in Algebra among Malaysian matriculation college students. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(2), 232–245.
- Elementary Teachers' Challenges and Coping Strategies in the Radio-Based Instruction and Modular Distance Learning. (2022). *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v9i2p240>
- Enitan, S., Adeolu, O., Olayanju, A., & Elejo, I. (2020). The 2019 Novel Coronavirus Outbreak: Current Crises, Controversies and Global Strategies to Prevent a Pandemic. *International Journal of Pathogen Research*, 4(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.9734/IJPR/2020/v4i130099>
- Fernandes, N. (2020). Economic Effects of Coronavirus Outbreak (COVID19) on the World Economy. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3557504>
- Gabriel, A. M. (2012). Enhancing Problem Solving Skills in Mathematics through Effective Instruction: A Literature Review. *Eurasian Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 8(2), 91-103.

Gabriel, E. D. (2012). Determinants of the mathematics performance of the fourth year high school students of sta. lucia district.

<https://www.slideshare.net/eugenedbest/determinants-of-the-mathematics-performance-of-the-iv-year-high-students-by-eugene-d-gabriel>

Gabriel, A. (2012). The Effects of Class Size on Student Achievement: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 4(1), 128-143.

Gautret, P., Lagier, J.-C., Parola, P., Hoang, V. T., Meddeb, L., Mailhe, M., ... Raoult, D. (2020).

Hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin as a treatment of COVID-19: Results of an open-label nonrandomized clinical trial. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 105949.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2020.105949>

Gonzales, J., Lucasan, K. L., Joana, D., Ocampo, S., Fontanos, N., Gonzales, J. F., Lucasan, K., & Ocampo, D. S. (2020). Revisiting Flexible Learning Options (FLOs) in Basic Education in the

Philippines: Implications for Senior High School (SHS).

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10698.18887>

Greenstone, M., & Nigam, V. (2020). Does Social Distancing Matter?

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3561244>

Guo, Y.-R., Cao, Q.-D., Hong, Z.-S., Tan, Y.-Y., Chen, S.-D., Jin, H.-J., ... Yan, Y. (2020). The origin, transmission and clinical therapies on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak - an

update on the status. *Military Medical Research*, 7. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-00240-0)

[00240-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-00240-0)

Gupta, S. (2021). Economic and educational implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Global Economics*, 28(4), 201-215.

- Guven, B., & Buket, O. (2012). Factors influencing mathematical problem-solving achievement of seventh grade Turkish students. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 23(1), 131–137. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271607678_Factors_influencing_mathematical_problemsolving_achievement_of_seventh_grade_Turkish_students
- Gwambombo, I. (2013). *The effect of teachers' workload on students' performance in community secondary school: A study of Mbeya City* (Doctoral dissertation). The Open University of Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. Retrieved from http://repository.out.ac.tz/913/1/IDDE%2C_GMhuruma_-_EXERNAL_-_OUT.doc_gabriel.pdf
- Heywood, E., & Ivey, B. (2022). Radio as an empowering environment: how does radio broadcasting in Mali represent women's "web of relations"? *Feminist Media Studies*, 22(5), 1050–1066. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2021.1877768>
- Horn, M. B., & Staker, H. (2014). *Blended: Using disruptive innovation to improve schools*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.
- Johnson, R. (2018). Education and its role in societal progress. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 52(1), 78-92.
- König, J., Jäger-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closures: Teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 608-622.
- K to 12 Toolkit. (2012). *Reference guide for teacher educators, school administrators and teachers*. Retrieved from http://www.seameoinnotech.org/eNews/Kto12Toolkit_ao17july2012.pdf

- Kumar, V. (2022). Transformation of education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(2), 145-159.
- Lee, J. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on the global economy. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 38(3), 211-225.
- Mohamed, L. & Waheed, H. (2011). Secondary students' attitude towards mathematics in a selected school of Maldives. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(15), 277–281.
- Malibiran, C. T. (2019). Mathematics Performance and Its Contributing Factors. *Journal of Educational Research and Extension*, 56(1), 13-30.
- Maristela, D. C., & Tuiza, A. V. (2021). Modular Based-Instruction Preparedness of Elementary School Teachers in Santa Cruz District Amidst the Pandemic. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 3(4), 169–179. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj218>
- Martinez, M. (2017). Investing in the education of young people for national development. *Educational Policy Review*, 30(1), 67-82.
- Mohammed, S. (2017). Relevance of Information Technology (It) To the Development of Distance Education. *European Journal of Open Education and E-Learning Studies*, 80–98. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.809488>
- Mohammed, A. (2017). Information Technology (IT) and the Growth of Distance Learning for Nigerian Instructors. *Global Journal of Education*, 4(3), 215-222.
- Ning, H.K, Downing, K. (2010). Connections Between Learning Experience, Study Behavior and Academic Performance: A Longitudinal Study.
- Nguyen, H. (2023). Challenges of education in developing countries during COVID-19. *Journal of International Development*, 40(2), 89-104.

OECD (2019), Mathematics performance (PISA) (indicator). doi: 10.1787/04711c74-en

OECD. (2019). PISA 2018 Results (Volume I): What Students Know and Can Do. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>

Ochwo, P. (2013). *Pupil, teacher, and school factors that influence student achievement on the primary leaving examination in Uganda: Measure development and multilevel modeling* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Ohio, USA: 12 Kiwanuka, Van Damme, Van Den Noortgate, Anumendem, Namusisi Kent State University. Available at <http://media.proquest>

Odhiambo, A. (2006). The Effect of School Factors on Student Mathematics Performance in Nairobi Province, Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 4(3), 517-538.

Ojose, B. (2011). Student Difficulties in Learning Mathematics. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 1(2), 43-48.

Phan, H. P., & Dang, T. (2017). Teacher readiness for online learning: Scale validation and measurement model. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 55(7), 942-967.

Quezora, V. M., Vasquez, A. G., Valencia, M. M., Joy, J., Capuso, R., & Capuso, J. R. (2022). PublicationsRadio-Based Instruction as a Support Modality: Its Effect on Pupils' Academic Performance During Distance Learning. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, 5(6), 128–132.

Qutoshi, S. (2018). Phenomenology: A Philosophy and Method of Inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*. Vol. 5, No. 1. DOI: 0528<http://dx.doi.org/10.22555/joed.v5i1.2154>

- Reeve, J. (2006). Teachers as Facilitators: What Autonomy-Supportive Teachers Do and Why Their Students Benefit. *The Elementary School Journal - ELEM SCH J.* 106. 225-236. 10.1086/501484. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/249134478>
- Reid, D. (2020, January 30). Coronavirus reaches Europe as France confirms three cases. CNBC. Retrieved from <https://www.cnbc.com/2020/01/30/coronavirus-reaches-europe-as-france-confirms-three-cases.html>
- Title: Teachers' Readiness for Distance Learning: A Review of Related Studies
- Rodriguez A. & Smith J. *Evid Based Nurs.* 2018 (2018). Phenomenology as a healthcare research method. Oct; 21(4):96-98. doi: 10.1136/eb-2018-102990. Epub 2018 Sep 10. PMID: 30201830. *Evidence-Based Nursing; 21:96-98.* retrieved from : <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30201830/>
- Rodriguez, E. (2022). Balancing healthcare and education in third-world countries. *International Journal of Development Studies*, 25(3), 187-201.
- Saavedra, A. (2020). Factors that Contribute to the Poor Writing Skills in Filipino and English of the Elementary Pupils. *International Journal on Innovation, Creativity and Change.* Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3697915>
- Sabio, R.A. & Sabio, C.J. Current Challenges and Prospects facing Distance Education in the Philippines. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 11(1), 59-77. Retrieved July 7, 2021 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/185236/>.
- Sanchez, H. S. (2012). The impact of self-perceived subject matter knowledge on pedagogical decisions in EFL grammar teaching practices. *Language Awareness*, 23(3), 220-233. Doi: 10.1080/09658416.2012.74908

- Soancatl, V., Lèon, A., Martinez, C, & Torres, L. (2010). Leading students to solve math's problems using question-led learning. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 4th European Conference on Games- Based Learning. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>
- Soancatl, G. M., Lèon, A. L., Martinez, O. G., & Torres, A. C. (2010). Effective Teaching Approaches and Strategies in Mathematics Education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 1536-1540.
- Smith, L. (2020). The role of education in achieving personal success. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 55(4), 201-215.
- Statement on the Philippines' ranking in the 2018 PISA results. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/12/04/>
- Suni, E. (2020) How Much Sleep Do Babies and Kids Need? Retrieved from <https://www.sleepfoundation.org/children-and-sleep/how-much-sleep-do-kids-need>
- Sunga, E.T. (2015). Determinants of Mathematics Performance of the Fourth Year Students in Public Secondary Schools in Pinamalayan. Thesis presented to the Mindoro State College Of Agriculture And Technology, Alcate, Victoria, Oriental Mindoro
- Tachie, M. F., & Chireshe, R. (2013). Factors Affecting Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Science in the Ejisu-Juaben Municipality. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(3), 115-128.
- Tadalan , C. (2021, February 1). *Coronavirus pandemic highlights failures of Philippine education BusinessWorld*. Business World. <https://www.bworldonline.com/coronavirus-pandemic-highlights-failures-of-philippine-education/>

- The case for children's rights to read. International Literacy Association (2018). Newark, DE: Author. Retrieved from <https://literacyworldwide.org/docs/default-source/resource-documents/the-case-for-childrens-rights-to-read.pdf>
- Tingley, J. C. (2012). *Talking aloud partner Problem-solving (TAPPS)*. Retrieved from https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/45119/12/12_chapterpdf
- Thompson, M. (2020). Addressing literacy challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Literacy Studies*, 22(1), 78-92.
- Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), ep2001. Retrieved from. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdll/8311>
- Tupas, F. P., & Linas-Laguda, M. (2020). Blended learning - An approach in philippine basic education curriculum in new normal: A review of current literature. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(11), 5505–5512. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.081154>
- UNESCO. (2017). Literacy. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/themes/literacy>
- UNESCO. (2020). Distance Learning Solutions. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse/solutions>
- Ventayen, R. J. M., et al. (2019). Teachers' Readiness to Implement Open and Distance Learning. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(3), 55-61.
- Wanjohi et al. (2011), "The Determinants of the Mathematics Performance of Secondary Education (KCSE) in Mathematics of Secondary Schools in Nyamaiya Division, Kenya"

Weiser, B. (2013). Effective Vocabulary Instruction for kindergarten to 12th grade Students Experiencing Learning Disabilities. Council for Learning Disabilities. Retrieved from: <http://www.council-for-learning-disabilities.org/publications/infosheets>.

Westerman, G., & McAfee, A. (2012). A major research initiative at the MIT Sloan School of Management Research Brief The Digital Advantage: How Digital Leaders Outperform Their Peers in Every Industry i. <http://digitalcommunity.mit.edu/docs/DOC-1105>.

Yeya, T. (2007). The Relationship between School Environment and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Bungoma East District, Kenya. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), 11-17.

Yousuf, A., & Islam, M. A. (n.d.). VIABILITY OF THE EXTENDED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY. In *Journal of ICT* (Vol. 10).

Zeeck, K. A. (2012). A phenomenological study of the lived experiences of elementary principals involved in dual-career relationships with children. St. Paul, MN: University of St. Thomas. Retrieved from : ir.stthomas.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1019&context=caps_ed_lead_docdiss

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter Request to School Division Superintendent Seeking Indorsement for Data Gathering and Conduct of the Study

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Los Baños, Laguna · (049) 536 6001

May 30, 2023

Schools Division Superintendent
Division of _____
Email Address: _____

Dear _____:

Greetings!

I hope this message finds you well. I am writing to seek your permission and support for my study entitled "Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal: Basis for a Proposed Innovative Workplan." This research forms part of the requirements for my Master's degree in Development Communication. Its primary objective is to explore the effectiveness and implications of radio-based instructions in the new normal educational environment, with a specific focus on how they influence motivation, job satisfaction, and commitment among teachers.

To accomplish this, I kindly request your permission to administer a questionnaire to selected Elementary, Junior High School, and Senior High School students in the schools of the Division of Cavite who have either implemented or experienced Radio-Based Instructions during the School Year 2021-2022. The attached study instruments provide a detailed explanation of how the research will be conducted. I assure you that the participant's responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality, and their anonymity will be fully protected.

I would be deeply grateful for your approval to conduct this study. Your support will contribute significantly to the successful completion of my research.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

CRISANTO E. AVILA
Researcher

APPENDIX B

Letter Request to RBI Teachers

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Los Baños, Laguna · (049) 536 6001

May 30, 2023

School: _____
District and Division: _____
Region: _____

Dear _____ :

Greetings!

I hope this message finds you well. I am writing to seek your cooperation and support for my study entitled "Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal: Basis for a Proposed Innovative Workplan." This research forms part of the requirements for my Master's degree in Development Communication. Its primary objective is to explore the effectiveness and implications of radio-based instructions in the new normal educational environment, with a specific focus on how they influence motivation, job satisfaction, and commitment among teachers.

To accomplish this, I kindly request your participation by administering the research questionnaire to your students who have experienced Radio-Based Instructions during the School Year 2021-2022. The attached study instruments provide a detailed explanation of how the research will be conducted. A link for the Google form will be sent to you and kindly facilitate your students in accomplishing the survey. I assure you that the participant's responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality, and their anonymity will be fully protected.

Your support will contribute significantly to the successful completion of my research. Thank you for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

CRISANTO E. AVILA
Researcher

APPENDIX C

Sample Indorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Region IV-A CALABARZON
City Schools Division of Dasmariñas

1st INDORSEMENT
June 08, 2023

REQUEST OF CRISANTO E. AVILA TO CONDUCT RESEARCH

Respectfully referred to the School Head of Dasmarinas North National High School in the City Schools Division of Dasmarinas, Dasmariñas City, Cavite with the information that the undersigned interposes no objection to the attached request of **Crisanto E. Avila**, taking up Master in Development Communication at University of the Philippines Open University, to conduct their research titled **“Radio-Based Instructions in the New Normal: Basis for a Proposed Innovative Workplan”** provided that utmost consideration to DepEd Order No. 9, s. 2005, titled Instituting Measures to Increase Engaged Time-on-Task and Ensuring Compliance Therewith, be observed and that no classes shall be disrupted in the conduct of the study.

For your information and appropriate action.

ELIAS A. ALICAYA, JR.
Assistant Schools Division Superintendent
Officer-in-Charge
Office of the Schools Division Superintendent

Attached: as stated
/KLM/053023-098

Address: CSDO Bldg., DasCA Compound, BuroI-II, City of Dasmariñas, 4115
Telephone No: (046) 432 7934 | 0919 081 4851 | 0919 081 4847 | 0919 081 4849
Email Address: dasmarinas.city@deped.gov.ph
Website: <https://depeddasma.edu.ph>

APPENDIX D

Memorandum of Agreement Request to Conduct Study and Gather Data

MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT REQUEST TO CONDUCT STUDY AND GATHER DATA

This Memorandum of Agreement is made and entered into between:

CRISANTO E. AVILA, 49 years old, married, Filipino, with principal address at Block 8 Lot 1 Phase 2 Extension, Mabuhay City, Paliparan 3 Dasmariñas City, Cavite, hereinafter referred to as the **FIRST PARTY**.

-and-

The **DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION – CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF DASMARIÑAS**, is a government entity created by law, with office address at CSDO Bldg. DasCA Compound, Burol II, Dasmariñas City, Cavite, represented herein by its OIC – School Division Superintendent, **MR. ELIAS A. ALICAYA Jr.**, hereinafter referred to as the **SECOND PARTY**.

WITNESSETH:

WHEREAS Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 was enacted to protect one's fundamental human right of privacy, of communication while ensuring free flow of information in order to promote innovation and growth.

WHEREAS the Department of Education recognizes the need of sharing data while ensuring the protection of one's personal information.

NOW THEREFORE, premises considered, the **PARTIES** hereby agree and stipulate on the following:

-
- 1. Purpose.** In entering into this agreement, the **SECOND PARTY** is granting the **FIRST PARTY** access to the Data gathered by the **SECOND PARTY**, for the purpose of conducting a research study on Radio Based Instructions.
 - 2. Description of Data.** The term "Data" includes information relating to personal, sensitive personal, or privileged information of an individual, whether a natural or juridical person, which was processed by the **SECOND PARTY** for the purpose of conducting a research study on Radio Based Instructions, data includes Demographic Profile of the Student Respondents, Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions to Students, and Problems Encountered by the Student-Respondents in RBI, further described in a research proposal, attached to this agreement
 - 3. FIRST PARTY's Use of Data**
 - A. Standard of Care.** The **FIRST PARTY** shall exercise at least the same degree of care as it uses with its own data and Confidential Information, but in no event less than reasonable care, to protect the Data from misuse and unauthorized access or disclosure.
 - B. Safeguards Around Data.** The **FIRST PARTY** shall use appropriate safeguards to protect the Data from misuse and unauthorized access or disclosure. Including:

- i. Maintaining adequate physical controls and password protections for any server or system on which the Data is stored;
- ii. Ensuring that Data is not stored on any mobile or transmitted electronically unless encrypted; and
- iii. Taking any other measures reasonably necessary to prevent the use or disclosure of the Data, other than as allowed under this agreement.

C. Personal Information. The **FIRST PARTY** will not attempt to identify any person whose information is contained in any Data or attempt to contact those persons.

D. Unauthorized Disclosure

- i. **Report.** The **FIRST PARTY** shall promptly report to the **SECOND PARTY** any unauthorized use or disclosure of data within twenty-four (24) hours of becoming aware of such incident.
- ii. **Cooperation and Mitigation.** The **FIRST PARTY** shall cooperate with any remediation that **SECOND PARTY**, in its discretion, determines is necessary to:
 1. Address any applicable reporting requirements, and
 2. Mitigate any effects of such unauthorized use or disclosure of the Data, including measures necessary to restore goodwill with stakeholders, including research subjects, collaborators, governmental authorities, and the public.

E. No Modification of Data. The **FIRST PARTY** shall not copy, decompile, modify, reverse engineer, or create derivative works out of any of the Data it will obtain by virtue of this agreement.

4. **Term.** This agreement will commence on the effective date agreed upon by the parties and will continue as long as the **FIRST PARTY** retains the Data, unless terminated earlier, but shall not exceed for five (5) years without prejudice to entering into a new data sharing agreement.

5. **Confidentiality/Security Measures.** The confidentiality of data pertaining to individuals will be protected as follows:

- a. The **FIRST PARTY** will not release the names of individuals, or information that could be linked to an individual, nor will the recipient present the results of data analysis in any manner that would reveal the identity of the individuals.
- b. The **FIRST PARTY** will not release individual addresses, nor will the recipient present the results of data analysis in any manner that would reveal individual addresses.
- c. Both parties shall comply with laws and regulations governing the confidentiality and privacy of the information that is the subject of this Agreement.
- d. The **FIRST PARTY** will not release data to a third party without prior approval from the **SECOND PARTY**.
- e. The **FIRST PARTY** will not share, publish, or otherwise release any findings or conclusions derived from their analysis of data obtained from the **SECOND PARTY** without prior approval from the latter.

6. **Ownership.** All data shared shall remain the property of the **SECOND PARTY**.
7. **Return or Destruction of Data and Property.** On the expiration or termination of this agreement, or on the **SECOND PARTY**'s request, the **FIRST PARTY** shall promptly:
 - a. Return the Data and any other property, information, and documents, including any Confidential Information provided by **SECOND PARTY**,
 - b. Destroy all copies it made of the Data and any other property, information, and documents, including Confidential Information, and
 - c. If requested by the **SECOND PARTY**, to deliver to the **SECOND PARTY** a certificate confirming the **FIRST PARTY**'s compliance with its obligation to return or destroy the Data mentioned under this section.
8. **Mediation.** The parties shall resort to mediation as a pre-requisite towards any possible legal action over all suits and actions arising out of this agreement.
9. **Venue.** The venue of all suits and actions arising out of or in connection with this agreement shall be within the Philippines where the agreement was entered into.
10. **Dissemination and Utilization of Data and Study.** The **FIRST PARTY** shall provide a copy of their study and obtained data to the **SECOND PARTY** which will be used for Planning and Research purposes of the Division.
11. The **FIRST PARTY** shall be held liable under Republic Act No. 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 for violating the terms and condition of this agreement.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the parties have hereunto set their hands this 9th day June 2023 at Dasmarina City, Cavite.

CRISANTO E. AVILA
First Party

CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF DASMARIÑAS
Second Party

Represented by:

ELIAS A. ALICAYA, JR.
Assistant Schools Division Superintendent,
OIC – Office of the Schools Division Superintendent

Witnesses

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

BEFORE ME, a Notary Public for and in CITY OF DASMARINAS CAVITE personally appeared the following persons exhibiting to me their Competent Evidence of Identity:

	Competent Evidence of Identity	Date/Place Issued
CRISANTO E. AVILA	PRC ID No. 21-5408010	PRC Manila, Aug. 25, 1998
ELIAS A. ALICAYA, Jr.		

known to me to be the same persons who executed the foregoing Memorandum of Agreement and they acknowledged to me that the same is their own free and voluntary act and deed.

I certify that the foregoing instrument, consisting of four (4) pages, including this page where the Acknowledgment is written, was signed by the parties and their instrumental witnesses on each and every page thereof.

WITNESS MY HAND AND SEAL this JUN 14 2023 day of June , 2023 at the City of Dasmariñas , Philippines.

Doc. No. 444 ;
Page No. 89 ;
Book No. 165 ;
Series of 2023.

ATTY. KAREN T. HERMOSA
NOTARY PUBLIC
Notary Public for City of Dasmariñas, Cavite
Until December 31, 2023
G/F K-Ann Bldg.
Cong. Ave., Drgy. Buro I, II,
City of Dasmariñas, Cavite
PTR No. 3413016; 01-03-23/Dasmariñas City
IBP No. 292698; 01-09-23/Cavite Chapter
Roll No. 41291
MCLE Compliance No. VII-0010387
Valid until April 14, 2025

APPENDIX D

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Name: _____

Direction: Please answer each of the following items by checking the appropriate box.

PART I: Profile of Student-Respondents

1. Gender: Male Female

2. Age: _____ 11 below

_____ 12 – 14

_____ 15 – 17

_____ 18 – 20

_____ 21 and above

3. Monthly Income of the Family

- 3,000 below
- 4,000 – 7,000
- 8,000 – 10,000
- 11,000 -15,000
- 16,000 – 20,000
- 21,000 – 25,000
- 26,000 and above

4. Parents' educational attainment:

1.1. Father:

- No schooling
- Elementary level
- Elementary graduate
- High School level
- High School graduate
- College level
- College Graduate
- With units in Masteral
- Master's Degree Holder
- With units in Doctoral
- Doctorate Degree Holder

1.2. Mother:

- No schooling
- Elementary level
- Elementary graduate
- High School level
- High School graduate
- College level
- College Graduate
-

- With units in Masteral
- Master's Degree Holder
- With units in Doctoral
- Doctorate Degree Holder

5. General Average obtained in School Year 2021-2022: _____

PART II: Level of Effectiveness of Radio-Based Instructions (RBI) to Students

Directions: Please evaluate and rate yourself honestly based on the statements provided, using the following scale:

5 – Extremely Effective 4 – Moderately Effective 3 – Slightly Effective
2 – Below Average 1 – Poorly Effective

A. AWARENESS AND PREPAREDNESS	5	4	3	2	1
1. I have a comprehensive understanding of the learning process of RBI.					
2. I am well-informed and knowledgeable about RBI.					
3. I am thoroughly prepared and organized before conducting RBI sessions.					
4. I can accurately assess the level of training and preparedness of teachers (Radio Broadcasters) for using RBI.					
5. I am fully aware of the designated radio station for RBI in both the school and district.					

B. AVAILABILITY AND CAPABILITY	5	4	3	2	1
1. I am aware that the school has a well-organized radio station.					
2. Radio is easily accessible in our home.					
3. I receive handouts and worksheets in a timely manner before the programs or sessions are aired.					
4. I am capable of following the program or session flow on RBI.					
5. I am capable of effectively learning through radio classes.					

C. TIME ALLOTMENT	5	4	3	2	1
1. Time management for the distribution and retrieval of worksheets is satisfactory for me.					
2. Both I and my parents are punctual in tuning in on time.					
3. I find the time schedule for every subject and session to be well-organized.					

2. Teachers exhibit a willingness to adapt their teaching methods and strategies to effectively engage students in the radio-based learning format.					
3. Teachers possess the necessary skills to design and develop educational content that is specifically tailored for radio delivery, maximizing learning outcomes.					
4. Teachers effectively communicate instructions, explanations, and examples through radio broadcasts, ensuring clarity and understanding among students.					
5. Teachers demonstrate efficient management of resources, materials, and assessment tasks, facilitating a smooth and organized radio-based distance learning experience.					
6. Teachers provide additional resources, supplementary materials, and follow-up activities that support students' understanding and enhance their learning outcomes.					
7. Teachers possess the ability to design and implement assessments that align with the unique demands of radio-based instruction, effectively evaluating students' progress.					
8. Teachers actively seek and participate in professional development opportunities related to radio-based instruction and remote teaching, continuously enhancing their skills and knowledge to better support their students' learning journey.					
B. Schools' Preparedness for Radio-Based Distance Learning Education Due to the COVID-19 pandemic	5	4	3	2	1
1. Availability of functional radio broadcasting equipment and facilities in the school.					
2. Strong signal coverage to ensure reliable transmission and reception of radio programs.					
3. Clear integration of learning objectives, content, and activities suitable for radio delivery.					
4. Adequate training provided to teachers on radio broadcasting techniques, instructional strategies, and effective use of radio as a teaching medium.					
5. Availability of a dedicated team or resources to develop high-quality educational content for radio-based learning.					
6. Regular production of engaging and informative programs that cater to different grade levels and subjects.					
7. Opportunities for students to ask questions, provide feedback, and participate in learning activities related to radio-based instruction.					
8. Ensuring that all students have access to radios or alternative devices to receive radio broadcasts.					
9. Regular evaluation of student progress and feedback to identify areas of improvement and adjust instructional strategies accordingly.					

10. Strong collaboration between school administrators, teachers, and parents to facilitate the smooth implementation of radio-based distance learning.					
---	--	--	--	--	--

THANK YOU FOR YOUR EFFORT AND COOPERATION!

Crisanto E. Avila

Researcher